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It is a great honour to me to extend my warm greetings and welcome you all to the journal, **Research Highlights**, a refereed journal of multi disciplinary research. The journal, which is a peer-reviewed, will devote to the promotion of multi-disciplinary research and explorations to the South Asian and global community. It is our objective to provide a platform for the publication of new scholarly articles in the rapidly growing field of various disciplines. We are trying to encourage new research scholars and post graduate students by publishing their papers so that they may learn and participate in literary publishing through a professional internship. Scholarly and unpublished research articles, essays and interviews are invited from scholars, faculty researchers, writers, professors from all over the world.

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Hoping all of you shall enjoy our endeavors and those of our contributors.

Editor

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Socio Economic Challenges of Birhor Tribe: Specifically in Jharkhand

Rashmi Oraon*

Introduction

The government of India recognises 730 group as Scheduled Tribe and 75 primitive communities who have been designated as 'Particularly vulnerable tribal group' based on their pre-agriculture level of technology, poverty, low level of literacy, poor economical condition, educational backwardness. PVTGs faces socio economic challenges despite Constitutional provision for their protection and development. PVTGs are found across 18 State and one Union territory in India including Andaman and Nicobar Island. In India the highest concentration of PVTGs are in specific states like Odisha, Bihar, Jharkhand, Andhrapradesh. In jharkhand there are 8 PVTGs these are Asur, Birjiya, Birhor, korwa, Malpahariya, parhiya, Sauria pahariyaand savar.

Birhor people are primarily found in Jharkhand particularly in the district of Ranchi, Hazaribagh, Dhanbad, Gumla, West Singhbhum, Khunti. They are also found in smaller number in parts of Odisha, Chhattisgarh, West Bengal and their lifestyle is way similar to each other. Birhor literally means the forestman. The word Birhor is derived by Combining two Mundari terms 'Bir' means forest and 'Hor' means Man. The Birhor of Jharkhand belongs to proto australoid group and linguistically they belong to Austro-Asiatic language family.^[1]

The Birhor people in Jharkhand have unique blend of animistic and Hindu religious belief. They also akin to those of the HOs, Mundaris deities' sun God ' that is " Sing Bonga" and " Hapram" that is " Ancestral Spirit " . While some Birhors have converted to Christianity but the majority still follows indogenous practices. Traditionally they live a nomadic hunting and gathering life style. They collect forest products like mahua fruits, leaves, wood. The Birhor settlement is known as "Tanda" that refers to a temporary settlement or a small group of 10-15 Birhor families.

The economy of Birhor tribe largely depend on hunting gathering, fishing, labour agriculture. Their agriculture land is divided into two major types- " Tanr" and " Don" Among Birhor their group is also known as " Killi". There are four type of clans in their community these are Maghaiya, Mudi, Mahali and Hembram but according to Roy 1925 there are only 37 clans among the Birhor in Jharkhand.^[2]

Socio Economic Condition of Birhor in Jharkhand

The Birhor tribe whose livelihood are totally depends on hunting and gathering are vulnerable tribe group of India. They face socio economic problems because of deforestation, modernization, and marginalization. The Birhors have a long history of Utilizing forest resources for their survival. They collect various forest products for food ,medicine, crafting tools and utensils. They also trap rabbit and titris a small bird and sell honey. They make rope from fibres particularly from " Bauhinia creeper " they sell in market. This is a significant traditional occupation to Birhor tribe. The Birhor tribe is traditionally classified into two groups based on lifestyle and socio economic status these are "Ulthus" means wondering Birhor and "Jangis" means settled Birhor.^[3]

The Birhor tribe of jharkhand faces significant health challenges including high rate of preventable diseases and limited access to health care. These problems arises due to lack of transportation and cultural barriers. They are also vulnerable to oral health issues like gum bleeding and tooth decay. Birhor primarily utilise "sakhua things" to clean their teeth.^[4] while some Birhor communities are leaving traditional practices for their well being. The Birhor have historically based on forest product for their sustenance but the "Satbadiya tanda" may be one of those who were experimenting with agriculture and less into foraging but it's not a wide spread practices among Birhors.

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Socio Economic Challenges of Birhor Tribe

The Birhos in India faces significant economical and social challenges including limited access to education, poor health care, unemployment,, low literacy rate lack of transportation, language and cultural barriers also witchcraft accusations where strong willed women may be targeted for challenging status quo, child marriage, complex problem, economically backward.

*** Low literacy rate :**

Birhors generally have low literacy rate in Jharkhand. Both male and female has poor literacy rate. They primarily live in forest and mountais and has no access to school other than Aagnawadi. The Birhos in Jharkhand faces low literacy rate due to many factors like poverty, cultural isolation, lack of awareness of benefit of education. The small children also work to support their family. Also school in Birhor inhabitant areas may be poorly equipped, lack qualified teachers, and school located far from village making it difficult for children to attend. Some families think it as a hindrance rather than a tool for advancement.

***Poverty:**

All families come under BPL and are living under very harsh conditions. Since they are mostly dependent on rope making, collecting woods from forest, and daily wage Labour as their source of income, which is very less to survive and grow.

***Inaccessibility:**

Though the village is located in forest or near to the Highway no local public or private transport are accessible to these community. They generally walk to nearby market .In emergency cases at nights or crisis situation things become way critical for community an causing danger for life.

*** Water and sanitation:**

"There is no government water supply in the hamlet. All the handpumps dug under government scheme, are malfunctioned. Community is dependent on the private water source dug.for domestic purpose they use water of well and pond as well. During rainy seasons, under lack of proper drainage system, communities get affected of water borne diseases.

***Limited access to education and heathcare:**

Low literacy rate and lack of access be quality education and healthcare facilities are major barriers to economic development.

***Poverty and equality:**

The Birhor community experiences high levels of poverty and inequality with limited access to basic services and resources.

***Loss of Traditional livelihoods:**

The traditional livelihoods based on hunting gathering and shifting cultivation are under pressure due to deforestation, encroachment, and changing land use patterns..

***Limited Employment opportunities:**

Lack of stable wage labour and Income generating oppantonities within the formal economy contributes to their economic vulnerability.

***lack of awareness about development:**

Limited awareness about government polices and development initiative prevents them from accessing the resources and opportunities.

***Cultural and language barriers:**

Due to language differences the people are not able to access education and employment opportunities provided by government.

***Lack of Transparency in Development funds:**

Lack of transparency in the auditing and accounting of funds allocated for their development raises concerns about the effectiveness of programs.

Availability of Land and Resources for Birhor Tribe

Birhors have historically had limited access to and Ownership of land, especially cultivable land due to their nomadic lifestyle. Some Birhor communities have settled and are now receiving land

allotment from the government. These allotment ranging from 3-25 dismil caber used for agriculture.^[5]

Marriage System in Birhor Tribe

The birhors believe that marriage is significant for the satisfaction of sex hunger and reproduction of children. It is also valuable for continuation of ethnicity from one generation to another. Naturally marriage with the same clan is prohibited but nowadays their rule of exogamy is not followed. Birhor family is patriarchal and patrilineal. The birhor follow the rule of tribe endogamy and clan endogamy.^[6] In birhor community the child marriage is very normal. For the first time hundred of birhor community members in jharkhand giridih district joined a movement against child marriage, a rampant practice within their country some campaigns are organised by government like "Bal vikash mukt bharat campaign" Launched by Union ministry of Women and Child development and some NGOs under JRC alliance. The ill effect of child marriage on children health, education, and over well-being were discussed to make birhor tribe aware of the social evil. JRC claimed to have stopped over 7000 child marriage in jharkhand between April and December 2024.

Education of Birhor Tribes of Jharkhand

The education of birhor is very poor. Generally they are illiterate, at present we see the first generation learner. Currently characterized by low education attainment, primarily due to factors like poverty, isolation cultural norms and distance of educational institution. Many children specially girls do not continue their education beyond the primary. The St. Robert high school in Hazaribagh is specially for birhor children sponsored by tata steel to provide free schooling for children who show a strong interest for education.^[7]

Religious Belief of Birhor Tribe

Birhors have a deep connection to nature and believe that mountains, forests, rivers and other natural elements are inhabited by spirits. They also believe that their ancestors spirit can influence their lives. They perform various rituals such as yearly congregational worship at sacred sites to appease deities and seek their blessings. The traditional magico - religious beliefs of birhors are akin to those of Hos, Mundari deities such as Sing Bonga that is sun god and hapram that is ancestral spirit.^[8]

The supreme god of Birhor tribe is the sun god and lugu buru lugu buru is mountain range. The Birhor tribe are living now very close to the santhals, Ho, munda, and Bathudi tribes^[9] currently 85% of birhors have adopted Christianity 15% are still practicing traditional religious belief and practices. In the chatani settlement all the household adopted Christianity but Durdura all younger generation have adopted Christianity. This religious transformation resulted into drastic changes in lifestyle as well as in practice.

Rope Making and Selling for Economy by Birhor Tribe

The Birhor tribe of jharkhand traditionally makes ropes using natural material like bark of specific trees and vines they also use plastic sacks for making rope. Rope making is a significant source of income for them. They started making rope 50 years ago. Plastic sacks were provided by tata iron and steel corporation to make rope they also keep goat, pig, hen, duck for their household of for economic purpose^[10] Mostly they make rope for pulling water from well. They take one day in making one bundle of rope. They sell it from door to door. They make "sikka" as per demand. It is made to hang utensils of food from roof. Women participation in their economic work is impressive. They do all the work of rope making same as their men.

Problems Faced by Birhors

- Their livelihood is only dependent on the occupation of rope making, and they earn very little which is not sufficient for their livelihood.
- Due to low literacy rate they are unable to access the scheme provided for their betterment by government of Jharkhand.
- They have no facilities of proper irrigation.
- Some of the Birhors are working as labours and tractor drivers. They are not practicing their traditional occupation.

- Deforestation make their life miserable as they completely depend on forest for their livelihood.

Schemes by Government of Jharkhand for Birhors

The Jharkhand government offers several schemes specifically targeting the Birhor tribe a Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Group (PVTG), to improve their Livelihoods and living conditions. These scheme include the PVTGs Dakia Yojna, Mukhyamantri Adim jan jati pension yojna and the Indira Awas yojna,harkhand Tribal Development Society ,Tribal Forest Dwellers Empowerment Scheme.

***PVTGs Dakia yojna:**

This scheme provides subsidized food grains to Birhor families, ensuring food security and improving living conditions.

***Birsa Awas yojna:**

This scheme provide housing to Birhor families.

***Mukhyamantri Adim jan jati pension yojna:**

This scheme provides financial assistance to adult, married women's, from primitive tribal families including Birhors.

***JTDS:**

JTDS facilitated the construction of permanent houses for Birhor households under the Indira Awas Yojna and the installation of solar powered water pumps in partnership with MECON and JREDA.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the Birhor tribe in Jharkhand faces significant social and economic challenges including Limited access to education and health care, high poverty rates and lack of employment opportunities. Traditional Livelihoods like hunting and gathering are threatened by deforestation and encroached lands while some Birhors have adopted agriculture, they often lack the resources and knowledge to succeed, leading to continued reliance on rope making and other traditional practices. Due to low literacy rate Birhor community faces challenges accessing scheme and benefit provided by government. Poor infrastructure, including inadequate road connectivity, is because of lack infrastructure.

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Impact of Parent-Child Relation on Anxiety and Insecurity among Children

Dr. Noori Jamal*

Abstract:

The present empirical study investigates the impact of parent-child relationships on children's anxiety and insecurity, with a focus on the differential roles of fatherhood and motherhood. Recognizing that parental interactions are central to children's socio-emotional development, this study examines how paternal and maternal acceptance influence children's psychological outcomes. A sample of 144 school-going children aged 10-15 years from Chhapra, Bihar, was selected through purposive sampling. Data were collected using the Sinha Anxiety Scale, Maslow Security-Insecurity Scale, and a structured Parent-Child Relationship Questionnaire, administered separately for fathers and mothers. Descriptive statistics, t-tests, and correlation analyses were employed to assess the relationships between parent-child interactions, anxiety, and insecurity.

Results indicate that both father-child and mother-child relationships are significantly associated with children's levels of security and insecurity. Children classified as insecure reported higher dependence on parental acceptance, highlighting the role of parental approval in emotional regulation. Regarding anxiety, paternal acceptance did not show a significant effect, whereas maternal acceptance was significantly higher among high-anxiety children, suggesting that maternal support may be more directly linked to children's management of anxiety. These findings underscore the differential influence of mothers and fathers: while both contribute to children's sense of security, mothers appear to play a more pronounced role in mitigating anxiety, whereas fathers primarily influence security and stability.

The study emphasizes the importance of balanced parental support in fostering children's psychological well-being. Implications for educators, counselors, and policymakers include the need for family-centered interventions that engage both parents to promote secure attachments and reduce anxiety among children, particularly within the Indian socio-cultural context.

Keywords: parent-child relationship, anxiety, insecurity, fatherhood, motherhood, school children

Introduction

It is often acknowledged that one of the most important factors influencing children's emotional and psychological development is the calibre of parent-child connections. Children's social behaviours, personalities, coping strategies, and general mental health are all influenced by their early interactions with their parents. While tense or conflict-ridden parent-child relationships frequently lead to maladaptive outcomes like increased anxiety, insecurity, and vulnerability to psychological disorders, safe and nurturing parent-child relationships promote resilience, confidence, and emotional regulation (Bowlby, 1988; Bögels & Brechman-Toussaint, 2006).

One of the most common psychological issues affecting kids and teenagers is childhood anxiety. Peer pressure, academic stress, and—above all—family relationships are commonly linked to it. Children who are rejected, overprotected, neglected, or have inconsistent parenting are far more likely to develop symptoms of anxiety, according to research (McLeod, Wood, & Weisz, 2007; Rapee, 2012). Similar to this, low levels of parental support and poor attachment quality are frequently the cause of emotions of insecurity, which are characterised as a lack of trust, stability, and psychological safety (Maslow, 1952).

According to McLeod et al. (2007), maternal connections are frequently defined by emotional warmth, nurturing, and prompt caregiving, all of which directly reduce anxiety by offering

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consolation and confidence. On the other hand, paternal connections usually place a strong emphasis on exposure to outside surroundings, discipline, and encouragement, which helps youngsters feel more secure and independent (Lamb & Lewis, 2010). This discrepancy emphasises the necessity of analysing mother-child and father-child relationships independently rather than using "parental influence" as a general term.

In the Indian sociocultural setting, the parent-child interaction is even more important because familial ties are seen as essential to a child's identity and growth. According to Sinha (1961), traditional attitudes tend to place dads as authority figures and mothers as the primary carers, which may have a divergent impact on children's emotional results. In order to improve the wellbeing of children, mental health practitioners, educators, and legislators can benefit greatly from examining these various parental roles in connection to anxiety and insecurity.

Standardised and trustworthy tools are necessary for the empirical evaluation of children's fear and insecurity. The Maslow Security-Insecurity Scale (Maslow, 1952) offers a recognised framework for assessing children's reported levels of security and insecurity, while the Sinha Anxiety Scale (Sinha, 1961) offers a validated instrument for measuring anxiety. When used in tandem, these tools enable a thorough analysis of the interactions between children's psychological states and parent-child relationships.

The current study aims to investigate how mother-child and father-child relationships affect children's feelings of anxiety and insecurity in light of this. Utilising standardised psychometric instruments and distinguishing between mother and paternal impacts, the study seeks to add to the expanding corpus of research on family dynamics and the mental health of children.

Literature Review

Parent-Child Relationships and Psychological Development

As the cornerstone of their cognitive, behavioural, and emotional regulating abilities, parent-child relationships are essential to children's socioemotional development. A stable attachment between a child and carer promotes feelings of safety, stability, and resilience, according to Bowlby's (1988) attachment theory. On the other hand, worry, low self-esteem, and trouble controlling emotions are frequently linked to insecure attachment styles. While authoritarian, negligent, or rejecting parenting is linked to poor developmental outcomes, research continuously shows that responsive, warm, and supportive parenting styles lower the risk of psychological illnesses in children (McLeod, Wood, & Weisz, 2007).

Parent-Child Relationships and Anxiety

A major contributing element to childhood anxiety disorders, which are among the most common mental health issues worldwide, is the familial context. Children are more likely to experience anxiety when their parents are too protective, critical, or insensitive to their needs (Bögels & Brechman-Toussaint, 2006; Rapee, 2012). In their meta-analysis, McLeod et al. (2007), for example, discovered a strong correlation between anxiety in children and bad parenting techniques. In a similar vein, Hudson and Rapee (2001) found that children's anxiety symptoms were increased when parents modelled frightened behaviour and over-control. These results demonstrate that youngsters pick up knowledge not only from face-to-face interactions but also from watching how parents respond to stress and danger.

Parent-Child Relationships and Insecurity

Children that are insecure exhibit feelings of instability, distrust, and vulnerability in social situations. According to Maslow's (1952) theory, security is a fundamental psychological need that is necessary for normal growth. The development of emotional stability in children is hampered by insecure parent-child ties, which are typified by uneven caring or rejection. This assertion is supported by empirical research, which shows that internalising symptoms like dread, withdrawal, and increased dependency are associated with insecure attachment (Kerns & Brumariu, 2014). Additionally, children from homes with a history of conflict or maltreatment report feeling more insecure than youngsters from supportive environments (Amato & Rivera, 1999).

Differential Influence of Mothers and Fathers

Even while both parents have an impact on their children's psychological health, the nature and extent of their influences frequently vary. According to McLeod et al. (2007), mothers have historically been the primary carers and providers of emotional support, which helps to prevent anxiety. According to Lamb and Lewis (2010), fathers, on the other hand, usually promote risk-taking, independence, and exploration, all of which help children feel secure and resilient. Amato and Rivera (1999) discovered a substantial correlation between children's emotional stability and less behavioural issues when their fathers were involved. Crucially, there is evidence linking a lack of a father figure to higher levels of maladjustment and instability (Flouri & Buchanan, 2003). This unequal effect emphasises how crucial it is to investigate paternal and maternal factors independently.

Cultural Context and Family Dynamics

The family is seen as the primary socialisation unit in many collectivist societies, including India. According to conventional conventions, mothers are typically given the majority of caring duties, with fathers acting as authoritative figures and suppliers of income. Sinha (1961) highlighted how hierarchical family arrangements and parental expectations had a big impact on kids' psychological development in India. According to recent studies, Indian kids with tense family relationships are more likely than their counterparts in more supportive homes to suffer from anxiety, academic stress, and feelings of insecurity (Malhotra & Patra, 2014). Therefore, analysing parent-child relationships in India offers insights regarding children's mental health that are pertinent to the situation.

Despite the fact that there is a wealth of research on parent-child connections and how they affect psychological outcomes, most of it has concentrated on Western nations. Furthermore, research frequently treats "parental influence" as a single concept, ignoring the different roles that mothers and dads play. Additionally, there is little scientific support for combining standardised psychological tests, like the Maslow Security-Insecurity Scale and the Sinha Anxiety Scale, to fully evaluate how anxiety, insecurity, and parent-child relationships interact in children. By methodically investigating mother-child and father-child interactions and their distinct correlations with anxiety and insecurity in school-aged children in India, this study fills these gaps.

Research Gap

Objectives

1. To examine the relationship between parent-child interaction and children's levels of anxiety.
2. To assess the association between parent-child interaction and children's sense of security-insecurity.
3. To differentiate the impact of father-child and mother-child relationships on children's anxiety and insecurity.

Hypotheses

Father-Child Relationship

H1a: A positive father-child relationship is negatively associated with children's anxiety levels.

H1b: A positive father-child relationship is positively associated with children's sense of security.

Mother-Child Relationship

H2a: A positive mother-child relationship is negatively associated with children's anxiety levels.

H2b: A positive mother-child relationship is positively associated with children's sense of security.

Research Methodology

Research Design

The present study follows a descriptive design aimed at exploring the impact of parent-child interactions and children's levels of anxiety and insecurity. The sample consisted of 144 school-going children (aged 10-15 years) selected through purposive sampling from schools in chhapra, Bihar. The sample included an equal representation of boys and girls to ensure gender balance. The total degrees of freedom (df) for inferential analysis were 142 ($N-2 = 144-2$).

Sinha Anxiety Scale (Sinha, 1961) was used to measure levels of anxiety among children. The tool has demonstrated satisfactory reliability and validity in previous studies. **Maslow Security–Insecurity Scale (Maslow, 1952)** is used to measure children’s perceived sense of security versus insecurity. It provides a useful index of psychological stability. A structured Parent–Child Relationship Questionnaire is administered separately for father–child and mother–child relationships, focusing on dimensions such as warmth, rejection, and support.

Prior permission was obtained from school authorities, and informed consent was taken from parents. The scales were administered to participants in group settings under standardized instructions. Responses were scored as per the manuals of the respective scales. Father–child and mother–child relationship scores were correlated with anxiety and insecurity scores. Data were analyzed using SPSS.

Findings

Table 1
Difference in Mean Scores of Accepting Fatherhood and Security–Insecurity

Group	N	Mean	SD	t	df	P value
Security	73	14.2	8.5	2.82	136	0.01
Insecurity	65	17.52	9.39			

Table 1 presents the difference in mean scores of Accepting Fatherhood with respect to Security and Insecurity groups. The analysis revealed that children in the Security group (N = 73) obtained a mean score of 14.20 (SD = 8.50), while those in the Insecurity group (N = 65) obtained a higher mean score of 17.52 (SD = 9.39). The calculated *t*-value of 2.82 with *df* = 136 was found to be statistically significant at the 0.01 level ($p < 0.01$).

This indicates that there exists a significant difference in mean scores of Accepting Fatherhood between the Security and Insecurity groups. Specifically, children classified as “insecure” reported higher scores on the Accepting Fatherhood dimension than their secure counterparts. This suggests that insecurity among children may be associated with heightened sensitivity or dependence on paternal acceptance, whereas secure children may not rely as strongly on paternal approval for their psychological stability.

Table 2
Difference in Mean Scores of Accepting Motherhood and Security–Insecurity

Group	N	Mean	SD	t	df	P value
Security	73	14.8	9.25	2.68	136	0.01
Insecurity	65	18.34	11.38			

Table 2 shows the difference in mean scores of Accepting Motherhood with respect to Security and Insecurity groups. The results indicate that children in the Security group (N = 73) obtained a mean score of 14.80 (SD = 9.25), while those in the Insecurity group (N = 65) obtained a higher mean score of 18.34 (SD = 11.38). The calculated *t*-value of 2.68 with *df* = 136 was statistically significant at the 0.01 level ($p < 0.01$).

This finding suggests a significant difference in mean scores of Accepting Motherhood between secure and insecure children. Similar to the fatherhood dimension, insecure children reported higher scores on the Accepting Motherhood scale compared to secure children. This pattern implies that insecure children may exhibit greater dependence on maternal approval and acceptance, possibly as a compensatory mechanism to cope with feelings of insecurity, whereas secure children may already possess a stable emotional foundation that reduces reliance on maternal acceptance for psychological balance.

Table 3
Difference in Mean Scores of Accepting Fatherhood and Anxiety

Group	N	Mean	SD	t	df	P value
High Anxiety	71	15.30	8.19	1.84	142	Insig.
Low Anxiety	73	16.20	8.01			

Table 3 presents the difference in mean scores of Accepting Fatherhood between children with high anxiety and those with low anxiety. The results show that the high-anxiety group (N = 71) obtained a mean score of 15.30 (SD = 8.19), while the low-anxiety group (N = 73) obtained a slightly higher mean score of 16.20 (SD = 8.01). The calculated *t*-value of 1.84 with *df* = 142 was found to be statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$).

This indicates that there is no significant difference in the mean scores of Accepting Fatherhood between children with high and low anxiety levels. In other words, the extent to which children perceive fatherhood as accepting does not appear to vary meaningfully with their level of anxiety. This suggests that factors other than paternal acceptance may play a more central role in influencing anxiety among children.

Table 4
Difference in Mean Scores of Accepting Motherhood and Anxiety

Group	N	Mean	SD	t	df	P value
High Anxiety	71	16.10	10.15	2.05	142	0.05
Low Anxiety	73	14.10	9.10			

Table 4 shows the difference in mean scores of Accepting Motherhood between children with high anxiety and those with low anxiety. The results reveal that the high-anxiety group (N = 71) obtained a mean score of 16.10 (SD = 10.15), while the low-anxiety group (N = 73) obtained a lower mean score of 14.10 (SD = 9.10). The calculated *t*-value of 2.05 with *df* = 142 was found to be statistically significant at the 0.05 level ($p < 0.05$).

This finding indicates that there is a significant difference in mean scores of Accepting Motherhood between high-anxiety and low-anxiety children. Interestingly, children with higher anxiety reported greater scores on Accepting Motherhood compared to children with lower anxiety. This pattern suggests that anxious children may show increased dependency on maternal acceptance or may be more sensitive to maternal behavior. It also implies that maternal acceptance plays a nuanced role in shaping children’s anxiety, possibly providing comfort yet also reinforcing dependence.

Discussion

The present study sought to examine the impact of parent–child relationships on children’s levels of anxiety and insecurity, with a specific focus on the differential roles of fatherhood and motherhood. Using the Sinha Anxiety Scale and the Maslow Security–Insecurity Scale, along with parent–child relationship measures, the responses of 144 school-going children were analyzed through descriptive statistics, correlations, and *t*-tests.

The findings highlight several important patterns. First, both father–child and mother–child relationships were significantly associated with children’s levels of security and insecurity. Secure children scored lower on both paternal and maternal acceptance dimensions, whereas insecure children reported higher dependence on parental acceptance. This indicates that insecurity in children is linked to heightened reliance on both parents’ approval.

Second, with respect to anxiety, the results showed contrasting trends. The father–child relationship did not reveal a significant difference in acceptance scores between high- and low-anxiety groups, suggesting that paternal acceptance may not directly influence children’s anxiety levels. In contrast, the mother–child relationship demonstrated a significant difference: children with higher anxiety reported greater acceptance of motherhood than their low-anxiety counterparts. This

implies that maternal acceptance plays a more direct role in shaping children's anxiety experiences, possibly due to the nurturing and emotionally expressive role traditionally associated with mothers.

Overall, the study confirms that parent-child relationships are vital determinants of children's emotional health, but the roles of fathers and mothers are not identical. While both contribute to children's sense of security, maternal acceptance appears more closely tied to the regulation of anxiety, whereas paternal acceptance exerts a stronger influence on feelings of security and insecurity.

Conclusion

These findings underscore the need for parents to provide balanced emotional support—mothers offering reassurance and fathers fostering stability—to nurture children's psychological well-being. For educators, counselors, and policymakers, the results emphasize the importance of family-based interventions that engage both parents in promoting secure attachments and reducing anxiety among children.

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Advances in Insect Vector Biology: A Zoological Perspective on Disease Transmission

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Abstract

Vector-borne illnesses remain a considerable challenge to global health. In recent years, there has been a rapid expansion of knowledge regarding insect vectors across multiple domains, such as molecular genetics, microbial symbioses, mechanisms of pesticide resistance, ecological responses to climate change, and advanced "omics" techniques for monitoring. This review synthesizes recent advancements (2018–2025) in insect vector biology from a zoological perspective, emphasizing how a mechanistic understanding of vector physiology, behavior, population dynamics, and microbiota contributes to the development of innovative control methods (e.g., Wolbachia replacement, CRISPR-based gene drives) as well as improved resistance management and surveillance techniques. An analysis is conducted on the advantages and limitations of different approaches, alongside considerations of ecological and ethical aspects. We also outline research goals aimed at decreasing the transmission of vector-borne diseases while minimizing ecological consequences.

Keywords: vector biology, mosquito, Wolbachia, gene drive, insecticide resistance, climate change, vector competence, surveillance, omics

Introduction

The study of insect vector biology focuses on understanding how insects contribute to the spread of infections, examining the biological, ecological, and physiological factors that influence this transmission process. An insect vector refers to an arthropod, such as a mosquito, sandfly, flea, or louse, that transmits infectious agents—viruses, bacteria, protozoa, or parasites—from one host to another, often without suffering any effects itself (Taylor & Francis, 2025). Understanding the mechanisms of insect vectors is crucial, as they play a significant role in the transmission of diseases such as malaria, dengue, Zika, leishmaniasis, and plague, which continue to pose major challenges to global public health (National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases [NIAID], 2023). The area of study focuses on key components, such as vector competence (the ability of a vector to acquire and spread pathogens), transmission methods (mechanical or biological), and the ecological and behavioral factors—like feeding habits, host preferences, and seasonal changes—that affect the spread of diseases (Beerntsen, James, & Christensen, 2000). Moreover, environmental factors including temperature, humidity, and pesticide resistance play a crucial role in influencing vector-pathogen interactions and the dynamics of disease transmission (Vontas et al., 2012). Recent advancements in molecular genetics, microbiome studies, and vector control techniques underscore the importance of understanding insect vector biology in developing sustainable strategies for managing vector-borne diseases (NIAID, 2023).

Insect vectors, primarily mosquitoes (*Anopheles*, *Aedes*, *Culex*), sandflies, tse tse flies, and certain ticks, play a crucial role in the transmission cycles of malaria, dengue, Zika, chikungunya, West Nile virus, and various neglected tropical diseases. Developing effective control techniques requires a comprehensive understanding of vector biology across multiple dimensions, including molecular, physiological, behavioral, and population ecology. Over the past decade, there have been significant advancements in vector biology and vector control science, driven by rapid technological innovations and new concepts such as high-throughput sequencing, microbiome research, gene

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editing, and enhanced ecological modeling. This study explores these developments through a zoological lens, highlighting the effects of changes in vector traits and environments on transmission, along with the ways in which novel therapies leverage vector biology.

Molecular and genetic tools: CRISPR, gene drives, and functional genomics

The emergence of CRISPR/Cas technologies in vector research has revolutionized the capacity to edit insect genomes, enabling the detailed analysis of genes that influence vector competence, host-seeking behavior, reproductive biology, and pesticide resistance. CRISPR-based gene drives are designed to alter inheritance patterns and spread traits throughout wild populations, presenting a potentially transformative approach to managing these populations by either replacing or suppressing them. Experiments conducted in laboratory settings and controlled environments have demonstrated the feasibility of suppression drives, such as those aimed at sex-determination genes. However, these approaches encounter significant challenges, including the emergence of resistance alleles, ecological variability, and a range of regulatory and ethical considerations. Recent evaluations and empirical studies highlight progress in the development of controllable, reversible, and confinable gene-drive designs, alongside an increasing emphasis on thorough risk assessment and modeling prior to any application in the field.

Zoological implications: Gene-editing experiments improve understanding of the physiological pathways that control vector behaviors (blood-feeding, host preference, fecundity) and pathogen susceptibility; however, the release of genetically modified populations requires careful evaluation of ecological interactions (predation, competition, hybridization) that could impact population dynamics.

Microbiome and symbiont-based interventions (Wolbachia and beyond)

Microbial symbionts significantly influence the physiology, immunology, and vector competence of insect vectors. The introduction (transinfection) of *Wolbachia* bacteria into *Aedes aegypti* and other mosquitoes has demonstrated notable reductions in the transmission of dengue and other arboviruses across various field experiments and practical deployment programs. *Wolbachia* modifies host reproduction (cytoplasmic incompatibility) and may reduce virus replication in mosquitoes—an effective biological control method currently implemented in multiple locations. Ongoing investigations are focused on strain-specific effects, environmental stability, *Wolbachia*–host–virus interactions, and the integration of these methods with conventional control strategies. Additionally, extensive microbiome studies are uncovering other bacterial, fungal, and viral associates that affect vector characteristics and could be leveraged for control purposes.

Zoological implications: Strategies that utilize symbionts rely on the compatibility of hosts and microbes, the pathways of vertical (and occasionally horizontal) transmission, and the ecological dynamics of host populations. Understanding the trade-offs in life history and the effects on fitness across different contexts is essential for predicting long-term trends.

Insecticide resistance: mechanisms and management

The increasing resistance of insects to insecticides threatens the efficacy of established vector control methods such as LLINs, IRS, and space spraying. Resistance arises through alterations at the target site, enhanced metabolic detoxification mechanisms, behavioral adaptations, and reduced penetration through the cuticle. Global monitoring has indicated that resistance is intensifying and disseminating to an increasing number of locations. This has resulted in updated WHO guidelines and methodologies for tracking and addressing resistance, including rotations, combinations, mosaic deployments, non-pyrethroid classes, and the application of non-chemical tools. Strategies for Integrated Resistance Management (IRM) that merge monitoring with operational planning are gaining significance.

Zoological implications: opposition Selection pressure, vector life-history, gene flow, and population structure each contribute significantly to the process of evolution. In developing enduring treatments, it is crucial to take into account ecological and evolutionary factors, such as metapopulation dynamics and fitness costs.

Climate change, landscape change, and vector ecology

Alterations in land use, urban expansion, and human migration, alongside shifts in climate, influence the distribution, seasonal patterns, and abundance of vectors. This alters the likelihood of disease occurrence and introduces vectors and illnesses to previously unaffected regions. Modeling studies and actual observations indicate that specific vectors are migrating northward and ascending in altitude, their seasonal patterns are shifting, and they are emerging in temperate regions. These changes necessitate flexible management strategies, ongoing monitoring, and forward-looking ecological models that consider climate, vector biology, and human behavior.

Zoological implications: The characteristics of a vector, including its growth rate, lifespan, and biting frequency, are influenced by temperature and humidity levels. Therefore, it is essential to develop mechanistic eco-physiological models that illustrate the responses of various life stages to microclimate for precise predictions.

Surveillance and 'omics' technologies

The emergence of high-throughput sequencing, metagenomics, and environmental DNA/RNA (eDNA/eRNA) techniques enables unbiased identification of diseases and vector species, monitoring of insecticide-resistance alleles, and characterization of vector microbiomes. The integration of these technologies, alongside mobile entomological tools, remote sensing, and AI-driven analytics, enables earlier detection of outbreaks and more precise mapping of vector populations. Recent studies employ genetic monitoring to infer population structure, migration patterns, and source-sink dynamics—information crucial for focused interventions.

Zoological implications: Genomics offers valuable insights into the connections within populations, their local adaptability, and the presence of cryptic species that exhibit different vectorial capacities, highlighting the need for modifications in targeted management techniques.

Behavioural ecology and vector competence

Factors such as genetics, age, nutritional state, previous blood meals, co-infections, and environmental stresses influence vector competence, which refers to the insect's inherent ability to acquire, maintain, and transmit a virus. The rates of human-vector contact are influenced by various behavioral characteristics, including host selection, feeding schedules, and resting patterns. Advancements in behavioral assays and neurogenetics are shedding light on the molecular underpinnings of host-seeking and feeding decisions, enabling the development of more effective attractants, traps, and spatial repellents. Integrating behavioral ecology with population-level models facilitates more accurate estimations of intervention effectiveness and the potential number of individuals who may fall ill.

Combining tools: socio-ecological integration and operational deployment

A universal solution does not exist. Contemporary vector control increasingly focuses on integrated vector management (IVM), which merges biological methods (Wolbachia, SIT), genetic strategies (gene drives, sterile males), chemical approaches (selective insecticides with IRM), and environmental management tailored to the local ecology and economy. Case studies illustrate significant reductions in disease burden when programs incorporate community involvement, entomological surveillance, and monitoring/evaluation. Regulatory frameworks, stakeholder participation, and ethical evaluation hold significant importance for the introduction of new gene-based releases.

Risks, ethical considerations, and governance

Recent interventions raise important ecological, ethical, and social considerations, including potential impacts on non-target species, horizontal gene transfer, enduring population suppression, equity in implementation, and the matter of consent. Governance frameworks must strike a balance between potential public health advantages and safety protocols. It is recommended that decision-making involve participation, risk assessment be transparent, testing occur in stages, and capacity be developed in regions where the disease is prevalent. The literature highlights the importance of a comprehensive approach that involves ecologists, entomologists, ethicists, regulators, and communities working together.

Research gaps and future directions

- Ongoing ecological assessment of symbiont-driven and gene-driven releases to discern evolutionary reactions.
- A deeper understanding of the interactions between the microbiome, vector, and pathogen across various environments.
- Improved gene-drive designs that are applicable in practical scenarios, encompassing safety and reversal protocols, along with robust resistance management frameworks.
- Advanced surveillance networks employing genomics, eDNA/eRNA, remote sensing, and AI to deliver early warnings and adjust control measures.
- Investigation in social science regarding community acceptability, ethical governance, and equitable deployment strategies.

Conclusions

Recent advancements in the biology of insect vectors have significantly enhanced our arsenal of tools for comprehending and halting the transmission of diseases. The field currently operates across a diverse array of scales, spanning from genes to landscapes. The focus encompasses molecular gene editing, microbiome modification, enhanced management of pesticide resistance, and ecological models informed by climate data. Achieving success requires the integration of detailed zoological understanding with effective monitoring, adaptable management practices, and governance that aligns with societal values. To transform biological advancements into sustainable

decreases in vector-borne disease burdens, it is essential to foster multidisciplinary inquiry and engage the community in the implementation process.

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Estimation of Electrical Conductivity Pentose and Hexose Sugar Contents in the Root, Stem and Leaf of 45 Days Old Mustard Plants Grown in Plain Soil and Amended Soil

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Abstract

Mustard is one of the major oilseed crops of India. It contributes major share in the total edible oil production of the country. Mustard oil is of the best edible oils available, having lowest amount of saturated fats as compared to the other vegetable oils. The electrical conductivity of root extract of 45 days old mustard plants grown in the soil amended with urea was more and was less when grown in plain soil. The EC of stem extract of 45 days old mustard plants grown in the soil amended with urea was more and was less when grown in plain soil. The EC of leaf extract of 45 days old mustard plants grown in plain soil was more and was less when grown in the soil amended with compost and urea. The pentose sugar of the root extract of 45 days old mustard plants in the soil amended with compost was more and was less when grown in the soil amended with urea. The pentose sugar of the stem extract of 45 days old mustard plants grown in the soil amended with compost and vermicompost was more and was less when grown in plain soil. The pentose sugar of the leaf extract of 45 days old mustard plants grown in the soil amended with compost was more and was less when grown in the soil amended with vermicompost. The hexose sugar of root and stem extract of 45 days old mustard plants grown in the soil amended with compost was more and was less when root less when grown in the soil amended with urea. The hexose sugar of the leaf extract of 45 days old mustard plants grown in the soil amended with compost was more and was less when grown in the soil with vermicompost.

Keywords: Plain soil, vermicompost, compost, urea, electrical conductivity (EC), pentose and hexose sugar, mustard plants.

Introduction

Mustard oil is an important component of the Indian diet. Mustard oil is used as condiments in pickles, flavoring curries and vegetables, hair oil, preparation of medicines and soap making. Intensive cropping has made the soil deficient in macro as well as micronutrients. This has resulted in decline in productivity and deterioration in soil health and productivity. Use of organic manures may prove a viable option for sustaining the productivity (Tajada *et al.*, 2009). Vermicompost application has been known to improve physical, chemical and biological properties of Soil (Nagavallema *et al.*, 2004). The long-term over cropping overuse of inorganic fertilizers without organic input degrade soil quality and health and cause environmental pollution as well (Albiach *et al.*, 2000). The application of organic fertilizer is an important practice in organic farming to improve soil quality, enhance microbial activity and nutrient recycle to produce high quality crops. Dimitri *et al.* (2012) reported that organic farming system produce healthy plants. Organic matter input into the soil gives a long-term positive effect due to humus production that can increase the soil action exchange capacity and water retention (Weber *et al.*, 2007). Jat and Ahlawat (2006) investigated that

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vermicompost application enhanced soil nutrient status (N and P) in subsequent crops compared to plain soil without vermicompost application. The effect of Vermicompost on plants was different compost is nutrient rich fertilizers, excellent growing medium for plants. Cow dung compost has balance NPK which is essential for plant growth. During present study attempt will be made to amend the soil using vermicompost, compost and urea and will be used as a culture media for mustard.

Materials and Methods

Plain soil was collected from the farm land and dried in sun for one week. The seeds of mustard was collected from Sarswati Beez Bhandar, Ara, Bhojpur (Bihar) Vermicompost was obtained from commercial sources. Compost was obtained from the farmer of Chandwa, Ara. Urea was obtained from the fertilizer shop.

Amendment of Soil: Soil was amended with vermicompost, compost and urea. The ratio between plain soil and vermicompost was 1:1. The ratio between plain soil and compost was 1:1. The ratio between plain soil and urea was 1: 0.25% (2.5g urea in 1 kg of soil). The amended soil was thoroughly mixed.

The amended soil was kept in earthen pots having capacity of 4 Kg each. Seeds were sown nearly 5 mm below the surface of the soil. Pots were placed in the open space of the garden. The seedling was cultured for 45 days. During this period the soil was moistened with tap water every alternate day. After 45 days of the seedling growth, plants were gently uprooted from the pots and washed it smoothly.

The electrical conductivity in the plant extract (root, stem and leaf) was measured with conductivity bridge maintaining the control of conductivity water : 2g of each sample of root, stem and leaf was weighed and extracted in 20ml of conductivity water by the help of mortar and pestle separately. 10 ml of plant extract was taken. The cell of the conductivity meter was dipped into plant extract and electrical conductivity was measured. The result of EC was calculated subtracting the value of conductivity water obtained for the extract of root, stem and leaf.

Pentose and hexose sugars in the extract of root, stem and leaf of 45 days old mustard plants were measured colorimetrically at 480 nm and 490 nm respectively using phenol-sulphuric acid method (Dubois *et al.*, 1951).

Results and Discussion

The amount in of EC of root extract of 45 days old mustard plants grown in the soil amended with urea was more and was less when grown in plain soil. The amount of EC of stem extract of 45 days old mustard plants grown in the soil amended with urea was more and was less when grown in plain soil. The amount of EC of the leaf extract of 45 days old mustard plants grown in plain soil was more and was less when grown in the soil amended with compost and urea.

The amount of pentose sugar of the root extract of 45 days old mustard plant grown in the soil amended with compost was more and was less when grown in the soil amended with urea. The amount of pentose sugar of the stem extract of 45 days old mustard plants grown in the soil amended with vermicompost and compost was more and was less when grown in plain soil. The amount of pentose sugar of the leaf extract of 45 days old mustard plants grown in the soil amended with compost was more and was less when grown in the soil amended with vermicompost.

The amount of hexose sugar of the root and stem extract of 45 days old mustard plants grown in the soil amended with compost was more and was less when grown in the soil amended with urea. The amount of hexose sugar of the leaf extract of 45 days old mustard plants grown in the soil amended with compost was more and was less when grown in the soil amended with vermicompost.

Table 1. Electrical conductivity, pentose and hexose sugar contents in the root, stem and leaf of 45 days old mustard plants grown in plain soil and amended soil.

Nature of Soil	Parts of Mustard Plant	Electrical Conductivity (mho/g fresh weight, Mean \pm S.E.)	Pentose sugar (mg/g Fresh weight, Mean \pm S.E.)	Hexose sugar (mg/g Fresh Weight, Mean \pm S.E.)
Plain Soil	Root	1.456 \pm 0.001	3.6 \pm 0.01	3.7 \pm 0.01
	Stem	1.345 \pm 0.002	3.2 \pm 0.01	3.4 \pm 0.01
	Leaf	1.943 \pm 0.001	3.5 \pm 0.01	4.0 \pm 0.01
Plain Soil + Vermicompost	Root	1.561 \pm 0.002	3.4 \pm 0.01	4.0 \pm 0.01
	Stem	1.521 \pm 0.002	3.6 \pm 0.01	4.1 \pm 0.01
	Leaf	1.936 \pm 0.001	3.1 \pm 0.02	3.4 \pm 0.01
Plain Soil + Compost	Root	1.923 \pm 0.001	4.0 \pm 0.01	4.1 \pm 0.01
	Stem	1.565 \pm 0.002	3.6 \pm 0.01	4.4 \pm 0.01
	Leaf	1.931 \pm 0.001	4.0 \pm 0.01	4.3 \pm 0.01
Plain Soil + Urea	Root	1.968 \pm 0.001	3.1 \pm 0.02	2.9 \pm 0.02
	Stem	1.596 \pm 0.002	3.4 \pm 0.01	3.5 \pm 0.01
	Leaf	1.931 \pm 0.001	3.7 \pm 0.01	4.0 \pm 0.01

These experiments, together with other reported in the literature, demonstrate that vermicompost and compost have considerable potential for improving plant growth significantly; when used as a components of horticultural soil. Nevertheless, there appear to be major differences between the effects of the vermicompost, compost and urea that were used in our study, in terms of their influence on plant growth depending upon the source of the parent waste material used in their production. Vermicomposting as well as composting releases most of the nitrogen in the nitrate form (Edwards and Burrows, 1988), the form readily available for plant uptake. There is accumulating scientific evidence that vermicomposts can influence the growth and productivity of plants significantly (Edwards, 1998). There was no report on the effect of chemical constituents in the plastic body when the mustard seeds grown in the soil amended with compost and urea.

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Women's Empowerment in India: Constitutional Aspirations and Realization

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Abstract

By 2036, India's population is predicted to reach 152.2 Crore, with a slightly improved female percentage of 48.8 percent as compared to 48.5 percent as in 2011 Census (MoSPI, 2023). In 2023–2024, India's women's work participation rate is 40.3 per cent, a significant rise from the previous rate of 22 percent (Periodic Labour Force Survey, 2024). Despite the increase in female population and their work participation, India ranked 129th out of 146 nations in World Economic Forum's Global Gender Gap Index in the year 2024, highlighting it as one of the economies with major obstacles to attaining gender parity (Global Gender Gap, 2024). Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) which serve as a roadmap for attaining a more sustainable and better future for all has included Gender equality as its fifth goal which aspires to eradicate all kinds of discrimination against women and girls worldwide.

Empowerment of women is a prerequisite for true gender equality (OECD, 2017). Women's empowerment is not only essential but also vital to the overall growth of society and the country at large. Consequently, it is imperative to enquire into the various facets of women empowerment in India along with focussing on the Indian Constitution which serves as a cornerstone for women's empowerment, enshrining principles of gender equality and non-discrimination. Hence, this study is aimed at examining women empowerment through the lens of Indian Constitution. It also highlights ongoing need for concerted efforts to fully realize the constitutional vision of women empowerment in India.

Key Words : Women Empowerment, Gender Gap, Constitution of India, Sustainable Development Goals.

1. Introduction

By 2036, India's population is predicted to reach 152.2 Crore, with a slightly improved female percentage of 48.8 percent as compared to 48.5 percent as in 2011 Census (MoSPI, 2023). In 2023–2024, India's women's work participation rate is 40.3 per cent, a significant rise from the previous rate of 22 percent (Periodic Labour Force Survey, 2024). Despite the increase in female population and their work participation, India ranked 129th out of 146 nations in World Economic Forum's Global Gender Gap Index in the year 2024, highlighting it as one of the economies with major obstacles to attaining gender parity (Global Gender Gap, 2024). Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) which serve as a roadmap for attaining a more sustainable and better future for all has included Gender equality as its fifth goal which aspires to eradicate all kinds of discrimination against women and girls worldwide.

Empowerment of women is a prerequisite for true gender equality (OECD, 2017). Women's empowerment is not only essential but also vital to the overall growth of society and the country at large. Consequently, it is imperative to enquire into the various facets of women empowerment in India along with focussing on the Indian Constitution which serves as a cornerstone for women's empowerment, enshrining principles of gender equality and non-discrimination. Hence, this study is aimed at examining women empowerment through the lens of Indian Constitution. It also highlights ongoing need for concerted efforts to fully realize the constitutional vision of women empowerment in India. This paper is divided into five sections, first section deals with background of the problem,

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second section deals with methodology followed in this study, third section briefly explains different aspects of women empowerment, fourth section enquires into different articles imbibed in Constitution of India associated with women empowerment, finally the last section discusses as to what extent constitution has played a role in shaping women empowerment in India.

2. Methodology

This paper is descriptive in nature and its methodology comprises comprehensive analysis of pertinent scholarly works and policy documents concerning women's empowerment in India and the role of the Indian Constitution in women's empowerment. The study focuses on constitutional provisions and various enactments are not under the purview of this paper which can be regarded as limitation of this study.

3. Aspects of Women Empowerment

The best way to combat exploitation, injustice, oppression and other issues that affect women is by the means of empowerment (Venkateswarlu, 2022). Hence, it is imperative to delve into the concept of empowerment. A wide spectrum of notions has been denoted through the phrase "Empowerment" by different scholars. Empowerment is the process of giving individuals or groups the ability to change a situation by providing them with the necessary tools, resources, opportunities, skills and authority for the same (Rodwell, 1996). Kabeer (2001) defined empowerment as "the expansion in people's ability to make strategic life choices in a context where this ability was previously denied to them". World Bank (2011) defined empowerment as 'the process of increasing the capacity of individuals or groups to make choices and to transform those choices into desired actions and outcomes'.

Bayissa, Smits and Ruben(2017) defined empowerment as expanding women's necessities and transforming these necessities into outcomes that have positive effects on women's well-being. Bushra and Wajih (2014) found out that the content of education, economic participation of women, poverty and economic opportunity available for women increases their empowerment. Table 1 illustrates different aspects of women empowerment and concerning indicators adopted by different scholars.

Table 1: Aspects of Women Empowerment

Dimension(s)	Indicator(s)	Author(s)
Economic Empowerment	Earning; Asset ownership	Sundaram, Sekar &Subburaj(2014)
Educational Empowerment	Freedom to decide about course to be studied	Tiwari and Malati (2023)
Familial Empowerment	Decision making power; secure from domestic violence	Jannah (2020)
Legal	utilizing the law to improve the circumstances of those who are disadvantaged and marginalized	Golub (2010)
Personal Empowerment	Power to negotiate	Mundhe (2021)
Political Empowerment	Political representation, participation in political campaigning; Influencing political decision; Voting rights	Venkateswarlu (2022)
Psychological Empowerment	Self-esteem; Internal Locus of control	Batool; Ahmed and Qureshi (2016)
Social(Socio cultural) Empowerment	Women's social relation and their position in social structure	Mandal(2013)
Technological Empowerment	Access to information; Communication	Niroo and Crompton (2022)
Source: Compiled by Author		

4. Women and the Indian Constitution: A Path to Equality and Empowerment

Women are given equality under the Constitution on every aspect. Additionally, constitution of India provides the government the authority to enact laws and formulate policies that would end all forms of cruelty, unfairness, and discrimination against women (Sharma, 2022). This section provides an overview of Articles imbibed in Indian constitution related with different facets of women empowerment and majorly focuses on Political Empowerment of women.

- **Article 14 Equality before law:** Within Indian territory, the State is not allowed to deny anyone equal protection under the law.
- **Article 15 Prohibition of discrimination on grounds of religion, race, caste, sex or place of birth:** Apart from other grounds this article prohibits discrimination on grounds of gender. Further, Article 15(3) provides that government can make special provisions for women which will not be considered as discrimination.
- **Article 16 Equality of opportunity in matters of public employment:** This article pertains to the equality of opportunity in terms of public employment. It declares that no citizen should be discriminated solely against on basis of their caste, decent, gender race, religion, place of birth, or any combination of these.
- **Article 39 Certain principles of policy to be followed by the State:** It specifies certain policy guidelines that the government must adhere to ranging from providing adequate means of livelihood and protection of citizen including women from abuse and that citizens are not compelled by financial need to pursue careers that are inappropriate for their strength or age along with **Article 39 (d)** is which states that government should ensure equal pay for both men and women.
- **Article 42 Provision for just and humane conditions of work and maternity relief:** The government must provide for maternity leave along with humane and fair and working conditions.
- **Article 51 Fundamental Duties:** Highlights duties of every Indian citizen includes Article 51 A (e) subpart which focuses on abstaining from practices which are derogatory of women (Government of India, 2024).

Political Empowerment of women includes their participation and influence in political decisions. The recasting of power in society is linked to participation as a tool of empowerment. Participation also means inclusion in the process of development, thus enabling the rise of underprivileged segment of the society (Venkateswarlu, 2022). At the most basic level, the Pachayati Raj Institution (PRI) promotes women's empowerment. According to **Article 243D (3)** of the Indian Constitution, SC, ST women must be granted at least one-third of the seats in each Panchayat that are up for direct election. These seats will be distributed by rotation among the Panchayat's several constituencies. At present PRI governs the village and is not merely an implementing authority but it has decision making powers.

According to **Article 243T(4)** of the Constitution, municipal chairperson positions are reserved for SC, ST women in a way determined by state legislatures (Government of India, 2024). Mehta (2022) has outlined that one of the major benefits of the 73rd Amendment's provisions regarding women's reservation of seats and political offices is that they have raised women's level of awareness and perception, which has encouraged them to claim their rightful place in local decision-making.

The hurdles in women's path of political participation in India include: Illiteracy which leads to lack of awareness among women about their fundamental and political right; Discrimination in Political Parties whereby women face unequal seat allotments in elections and are underrepresented in party ranks; Patriarchal Society which is the pervasive patriarchal context which limits women's involvement in politics; Societal Value System where existing societal norms restrict their political engagement; Lack of resource as the women have unequal access to resources necessary for political activities, including financial support from parties; Traditional Roles whereby societal expectations

confine women to traditional roles, hampering their political aspirations and lastly Cultural Norms which pressures often bar women from entering politics, compelling them to conform to imposed roles. (Venkateswarlu, 2021).

Global Gender Gap report (2024) elucidates that head-of-state indicator (40.7 per cent) places India in the top 10 of the Political Empowerment sub index. Though India continues to have relatively low scores for women's representation in parliament (17.2 per cent) and at the federal level in ministerial positions (6.9 per cent).

While enquiring into participation of women in the Lok Sabha elections 2024, as voters as well as candidates it was highlighted that female voters turnout outnumbered male voters turnout as 65.78 per cent of female voters voted compared to 65.55 percent of male voters turnout. On the side of contestants, out of total 543 parliamentary constituencies 152 parliamentary constituency were such that there were no female contesting candidates. Three states in India having highest female candidates were Maharashtra where number of female contesting candidates were 111 followed by Uttar Pradesh with 80 female contestant along with Tamil Nadu with 77 contestants.

While the number of female candidates elected was 74 out of total 543 parliamentary constituencies. The top five State or Union Territories with highest share of elected female candidates were Tripura with 50.0 per cent, Dadra and Nagar Haveli and Daman and Diu with 50.0 per cent followed by National Capital Territory Delhi with 28.6 per cent, Chhattisgarh with 27.3 per cent and West Bengal with 26.2 per cent. Hence, it can be said that there is awareness among women in India with regard to their voting rights as evident from their high number of voter turnout but on the front of contesting as candidates in elections there is long way ahead as approximately 29 per cent of parliamentary constituency did not had women contestant. Policies should be framed by government and other stakeholder should work to reduce the barriers to women's participation which could result in political empowerment of women.

5. Conclusions

Notwithstanding the Constitution's directive for social justice and guarantee of gender equality, widespread prejudice and exploitative treatment of women persist. The government has repeatedly enacted numerous new legislation and taken other actions to empower women but there is long way ahead. If it is ensured that the spirit of constitution is followed then it will lead to the fulfilment of women empowerment goal. Policies should be framed by government and other stakeholder should work to reduce the barriers to women's participation which could result in political empowerment of women, similarly steps should be taken to improve other facets of women empowerment.

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Henry James: A Literary Life and Legacy

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Abstract

Henry James (1843–1916), a seminal figure in American and transatlantic literature, shaped the modern novel through his exploration of psychological depth, narrative innovation, and aesthetic theory. This study examines James's literary evolution across three major phases—early, middle, and late—highlighting his signature “international theme” and his portrayals of cultural conflict between American innocence and European sophistication in works like *The American*, *Daisy Miller*, and *The Portrait of a Lady*. His later masterpieces, including *The Wings of the Dove* and *The Ambassadors*, showcase stylistic refinement and interior consciousness. As a critic, James advocated artistic freedom and formal precision, opposing moral didacticism in fiction. Through an analysis of his fiction, dramatic efforts, and critical writings especially *The Art of Fiction* this article underscores James's enduring legacy as a novelist, thinker, and craftsman of literary realism.

Keywords : American literature, Transatlantic fiction, Psychological realism, The international theme, Modern novel, Narrative technique, Aesthetic theory, The Art of Fiction, Cultural conflict, Literary criticism, European influence, Consciousness in fiction, Edith Wharton, Realism and modernism.

Henry James, a distinguished American novelist, critic, and thinker, was born in New York in 1843. He was the younger brother of William James, the eminent philosopher and psychologist. Educated in various cities including Newport, Boulogne, Paris, Geneva, and Bonn, James received a cosmopolitan upbringing that would deeply inform his later literary themes. After briefly enrolling at Harvard Law School in 1862, James soon abandoned legal studies, encouraged by mentors such as Charles Eliot Norton and William Dean Howells, to pursue literature full-time (Edel, Leon, 1985, pp.35–37).

James began his career writing travel sketches and journalistic pieces. In 1875, he spent time in Paris before settling permanently in England in 1876, where he resided primarily in London for over two decades. In 1915, he formally became a British citizen, and he remained in England until his death in 1917. His literary circle was vast and included major figures such as Joseph Conrad, H. G. Wells, George Gissing, Stephen Crane, and Edith Wharton, with whom he shared a particularly close friendship in his later years (Tintner, Adeline R., 2000, p.92).

James's early novels often explored the American encounter with Europe, a theme that underpins *The American* (1877), *The Europeans* (1878), *Daisy Miller* (1879), and *The Portrait of a Lady* (1881), the latter being considered a pinnacle of his early achievement. He was also deeply influenced by European writers such as Émile Zola, Gustave Flaubert, and the Goncourt brothers, as well as the Polish-born Joseph Conrad, with whom he shared philosophical and stylistic affinities (Bradbury and McFarlane 344).

James continued to develop his “international theme” in works such as *Washington Square* (1880), *The Bostonians* (1886), and *The Princess Casamassima* (1886). He also contributed significantly to literary criticism, with notable works including *Partial Portraits* (1888), *Portraits of Places* (1883), *French Poets and Novelists* (1878), and *Hawthorne* (1879). His essay *The Art of Fiction* (1884) articulates his aesthetic credo, advocating for narrative freedom and artistic integrity.

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Despite his critical acclaim, James's theatrical endeavours were not well received. After the relative failure of his stage plays, he returned to fiction with a renewed stylistic complexity in novels such as *The Spoils of Poynton* (1897), *What Maisie Knew* (1897), *The Awkward Age* (1899), and *The Sacred Fount* (1901). His late masterpieces include *The Turn of the Screw* (1898), *The Wings of the Dove* (1902), *The Ambassadors* (1903), and *The Golden Bowl* (1904), all of which showcase his elaborate syntax and exploration of consciousness.

James's biographer Leon Edel divides his literary career into three phases: the early period (*Daisy Miller*, *The Portrait of a Lady*), the middle period (*The Bostonians*, *The Princess Casamassima*), and the late phase (*The Wings of the Dove*, *The Ambassadors*, *The Golden Bowl*), where his stylistic and psychological depth reached its zenith (Edel, Leon, 1955, pp.103–04).

First serialised in *The Atlantic Monthly* in 1876 and published in book form in 1877, *The American* centres on Christopher Newman, a wealthy, self-made American industrialist who travels to Paris seeking cultural refinement and a European bride. Despite his success in business, Newman is naive about European aristocratic customs, a thematic tension James explores with irony and insight (James, Henry, 1981, pp.14–17).

Newman courts Claire de Cintré, a widowed member of the noble Bellegarde family. However, once Claire's family discovers Newman's background and wealth-driven motives, they annul the engagement to preserve their lineage. The subplot involving Noémie Nioche, a manipulative copyist, and Valentin Bellegarde, Claire's brother and Newman's confidant, leads to a tragic duel. Despite possessing evidence of the Bellegardes' moral corruption, Newman refrains from using it for retribution, and the novel concludes with Claire entering a Carmelite convent—more from resignation than religious conviction (James 265–89).

Literary critic Harry T. Moore observes that while the theme of an American confronting European social codes was familiar to French readers, James enriched it with psychological complexity and narrative elegance (Moore, Harry T., 1965, p. 211).

In 1890, actor Edward Compton, husband of American actress Virginia Bateman and father of future novelist Sir Compton Mackenzie, proposed adapting *The American* for the stage. The play premiered in Liverpool and altered the plot to include a happier ending: Valentin survives, and Newman marries Claire. Though performed by notable actors such as Elizabeth Robins and Edward Compton himself, the play failed to impress London audiences, who found its structure more akin to a drawing-room comedy than compelling drama (Tintner, Adeline R., 2000, p. 133).

Henry James's *Daisy Miller* (1879) is a novella that explores the conflict between innocence and social convention within the expatriate American community in Europe. The eponymous protagonist, Daisy Miller, is travelling through Europe with her mother and younger brother. Her open manner, youthful spontaneity, and disregard for rigid European etiquette are misinterpreted as moral impropriety by the conservative American expatriates. However, Frederick Winterbourne, a reserved and somewhat ambiguous American gentleman, becomes intrigued by her freshness and apparent purity.

While in Rome, Daisy forms a close companionship with an Italian named Giovanelli, which further isolates her from the expatriate community. Winterbourne encounters the pair at the Colosseum under the moonlight and, in a display of social caution, warns Daisy that such behaviour is inappropriate and that she risks contracting "Roman fever" (malaria). Distressed by his judgement, Daisy returns to her hotel, falls ill with the fever, and tragically dies a few days later (James, *Daisy Miller* 57–62).

The theme of moral misjudgement and tragic misunderstanding is closely akin to that of Edith Wharton's *Roman Fever* (1934), a work written by James's friend and literary admirer. Wharton also critiques rigid societal norms and their fatal consequences for women's autonomy and emotional lives (Lewis 112).

James adapted *Daisy Miller* into a play for the New York stage, but it was rejected on the grounds that the content was too intellectually nuanced for popular theatre (Edel, *Henry James: A Life* 284).

Washington Square was first serialised in *The Cornhill Magazine* and later published in 1880. The novel centres on Catherine Sloper, the plain but wealthy daughter of a successful New York physician, Dr. Austin Sloper. Catherine's life is colourless and uneventful until she becomes romantically involved with the charming but penniless Morris Townsend. Although she falls in love with him and accepts his proposal, her father refuses to approve the marriage, convinced that Townsend is motivated purely by financial interest.

In an effort to dissuade her, Dr. Sloper takes Catherine on an extended tour of Europe. Despite this, she remains steadfast in her affection. However, Townsend ultimately abandons the engagement when he realises he will not gain access to her inheritance. Seventeen years later, following her father's death and her inheritance of a fortune, Townsend reappears and proposes once more. Catherine, emotionally hardened by betrayal and solitude, refuses him without hesitation and chooses a life of independence (James, *Washington Square* 135–142).

Henry James famously commented on the “*air of reality*” in fiction as its supreme virtue. He insisted that “*the novel is history seen through a temperament*,” thereby elevating the moral and psychological realism of fiction over authorial intrusion (James, *Washington Square* 31, 33). He was particularly critical of novelists like Anthony Trollope, who addressed the reader directly, thereby breaking the immersive illusion of fiction: “*I can't forgive Trollope... for breaking the illusion by talking about his characters as if they are unreal*” (James, *Washington Square* 26).

James's approach to narration contributed significantly to the evolution of the modern novel. In his prefaces and critical essays, he advocated the elimination of the omniscient narrator's intrusive commentary. As critic Joseph Warren Beach observes, “*If you look at the English novel from Fielding to Ford from a bird's-eye view, the author's disappearance is the most striking change*” (Beach 117). In earlier writers like Fielding, Scott, Thackeray, and Eliot, the narrator acted as moral guide, philosopher, and commentator. James resisted this didactic approach, asserting instead that “*anything is better for artistic participation than irresponsible authorship*” (James, *The Art of the Novel* 59).

James also likened the novelist to a painter or dramatist. He highlighted the importance of *form, structure, and framing*—arguing that “*art is all selection and bias; reality is all confusion and multiplicity*” (James, *The Art of the Novel* 101). The novelist's duty, therefore, is not merely to transcribe reality but to *render it with imaginative coherence* and artistic restraint: “*The artist's task is to draw the circle within which the connection seems complete, even if in life it never is*” (James, *The Art of the Novel* 120).

Such reflections show James's effort to align fiction with the disciplines of visual art and philosophy. He conceptualised the novelist as historian, dramatist, and interpreter of life—an artist who constructs meaning out of chaos. His critical work *The Art of Fiction* (1884) laid the theoretical foundation for his mature narrative strategies, whereas the later *Prefaces* (1907–1909) reflect his self-assessment and aesthetic refinement.

James's *The Portrait of a Lady* (1881) remains, in his own view, among his most architecturally perfect novels, second only to *The Ambassadors* (1903): “*The Portrait is, to my sense, the most proportioned of my productions after The Ambassadors*” (James, *The Art of the Novel* 300).

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The Role of Social Media in Shaping Self-Concept and Identity

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Abstract:

This study examines the influence of social media on self-concept and identity among adolescents and young adults. Using a mixed-methods design, quantitative data were collected through standardized scales measuring self-concept clarity, self-esteem, and social media usage, while qualitative insights were obtained through semi-structured interviews. The results indicate that higher social media usage is associated with reduced self-concept clarity and increased dependency on external validation. Descriptive and inferential statistics, including mean, standard deviation, and t-tests, revealed significant gender differences in patterns of online identity expression. Qualitative findings further suggest that individuals negotiate a balance between online and offline selves, with social comparison playing a crucial role. The study highlights the dual nature of social media, functioning both as a platform for identity exploration and as a source of identity conflict.

Keywords: Social media, self-concept clarity, identity formation, self-esteem, social comparison, adolescents, young adults

Introduction

Identity and self-concept form the foundation of psychological well-being and social functioning. Self-concept refers to the perception individuals hold about themselves, encompassing values, beliefs, and social roles. Identity extends this perception by situating individuals within social contexts and cultural frameworks. In the 21st century, social media has become a primary arena where self-concept and identity are constructed, negotiated, and displayed.

Platforms such as Instagram, TikTok, and Facebook offer opportunities for curated self-presentation, enabling individuals to project idealized versions of themselves while receiving feedback through likes, comments, and followers. While these processes may foster self-expression and belongingness, they also raise concerns regarding authenticity, social comparison, and self-esteem. The present study investigates the role of social media in shaping self-concept and identity, with particular attention to the effects of online validation and gender-based differences in identity expression.

Review of Literature

The intersection of social media, self-concept, and identity has become one of the most studied areas in psychology, given the ubiquity of digital platforms in everyday life. Existing research reveals both positive and negative implications of social media use, depending on the intensity of engagement, the purpose of usage, and the demographic characteristics of users.

Theoretical Perspectives

Social comparison theory (Festinger, 1954) remains foundational in understanding social media's impact. On platforms where users are constantly exposed to idealized portrayals of others, individuals are likely to engage in upward comparison, which can undermine self-esteem and self-concept clarity. Higgins' (1987) self-discrepancy theory provides further explanation, arguing that inconsistencies between one's actual, ideal, and ought selves can generate feelings of inadequacy. Social media amplifies these discrepancies by allowing individuals to craft "ideal selves" online, often at odds with offline realities.

Goffman's (1959) dramaturgical framework conceptualizes self-presentation as a performance, in which individuals actively manage impressions before an audience. Social media serves as a "front stage" where users showcase curated identities while concealing less desirable

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aspects in the “back stage.” This performance-based identity construction raises questions about authenticity and psychological adjustment. Similarly, Erikson’s (1968) psychosocial theory emphasizes identity formation during adolescence and young adulthood, a stage when social media now plays an integral role in exploration and role experimentation.

Self-Concept and Identity Development

Research demonstrates that self-concept clarity—defined as the extent to which beliefs about oneself are clearly and confidently defined, internally consistent, and temporally stable (Campbell et al., 1996)—is particularly sensitive to online environments. Valkenburg and Peter (2011) note that online interactions allow adolescents to experiment with multiple aspects of their identities, providing opportunities for self-discovery. However, such experimentation can also fragment identity, resulting in a lack of coherence.

A growing body of evidence links social media use with body image concerns and self-objectification. Perloff (2014) found that young women are especially vulnerable to body dissatisfaction due to exposure to idealized images and the constant reinforcement of appearance-related feedback. Tiggemann and Slater (2017) further showed that image-based platforms such as Instagram foster a culture of comparison, which negatively affects self-concept and contributes to identity struggles.

Validation and Feedback

Validation through likes, comments, and followers has been identified as a significant factor in shaping self-esteem. Valkenburg, Peter, and Schouten (2006) argue that feedback received online can temporarily enhance self-esteem, but dependence on external validation creates instability in self-concept. Gonzales and Hancock (2011) demonstrated that social media profiles can boost self-esteem when individuals receive positive feedback, though these effects are often short-lived.

Gender and Cultural Differences

Gender differences are particularly notable in online identity presentation. Females tend to emphasize physical attractiveness and relational aspects of identity, whereas males highlight achievements, humor, and independence (Manago et al., 2008). These differences partly explain why females report lower self-concept clarity and greater body dissatisfaction in relation to social media.

Cultural context also shapes the relationship between social media and identity. In collectivist societies, online identity may be constructed with greater reference to group belongingness, while in individualist cultures, identity expression often emphasizes uniqueness and independence (Chen, 2013). This suggests that the psychological impact of social media cannot be generalized universally but must be understood in specific socio-cultural frameworks.

Positive Aspects of Social Media

Despite concerns, social media also provides important opportunities for identity development. Davis (2012) argues that platforms enable “identity play,” allowing adolescents to test out different roles in relatively safe environments. Similarly, social media can strengthen identity by facilitating belongingness and community engagement, particularly for marginalized groups who find affirmation online (McKenna & Bargh, 2000).

Emerging Concerns

Recent research has drawn attention to the addictive qualities of social media use. Andreassen et al. (2017) suggest that excessive engagement with social media can lead to addictive behaviors, which, in turn, affect psychological well-being and identity stability. Twenge and Campbell (2018) reported that adolescents spending more than three hours daily on social media exhibited lower levels of happiness and psychological adjustment. These findings point to a critical balance between the benefits of digital self-expression and the risks of overuse.

Objectives

1. To assess the relationship between social media use and self-concept clarity.
2. To examine the role of online validation and social comparison in shaping self-esteem.
3. To identify gender differences in patterns of identity expression online.

4. To analyze how individuals reconcile online and offline identities.

Hypothesis

- H1: Higher social media use is associated with lower self-concept clarity.
 H2: Positive feedback (likes, comments) increases self-esteem temporarily but may reinforce dependency on external validation.
 H3: Females are more likely than males to engage in appearance-based identity presentation.

Methodology

A descriptive and analytical design was employed, incorporating both quantitative and qualitative methods. The study sample consisted of 200 participants (100 male, 100 female) aged 15–25, drawn from universities and colleges. Stratified random sampling was used to ensure gender balance. Self-Concept Clarity Scale (SCCS) was used to measure consistency of self-concept. Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (RSES) was used to assess global self-esteem. Social Media Usage Questionnaire was used for measuring daily usage, preferred platforms, and perceived importance of online validation. Participants completed the questionnaires anonymously. A subset of 20 participants was interviewed to gain qualitative insights into identity presentation and authenticity. Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean, SD) and independent sample t-tests. Qualitative data were analyzed thematically.

Analysis and Findings

Table 1 : Descriptive Statistics of Key Variables (N = 200)

Variable	M	SD	Minimum	Maximum
Social Media Usage (hrs/day)	4.85	1.72	1.0	9.5
Self-Concept Clarity (SCCS)	32.41	6.25	18.0	48.0
Self-Esteem (RSES)	21.75	4.92	10.0	30.0
Social Comparison Tendency	15.28	3.87	8.0	24.0

Table 1 shows that participants spent an average of 4.85 hours daily on social media, reflecting heavy engagement. The moderate mean scores for self-concept clarity (M = 32.41) and self-esteem (M = 21.75) suggest that identity stability and self-worth varied across individuals. The relatively high score for social comparison (M = 15.28) indicates frequent evaluative tendencies. These findings provide preliminary support for Hypothesis 1, which proposed that higher social media use is associated with lower self-concept clarity, and for Hypothesis 2, which anticipated that validation and comparison processes could impact self-esteem.

Table 2 : Gender Differences in Social Media Use and Self-Concept (Independent Samples t-test, N = 200)

Variable	Gender	M	SD	t	p
Social Media Usage (hrs/day)	Male (n = 90)	4.32	1.55	-3.11	.002
	Female (n = 110)	5.28	1.78		
Self-Concept Clarity	Male	34.10	6.02	2.45	.015
	Female	31.15	6.28		
Self-Esteem	Male	22.84	4.75	2.98	.003
	Female	20.92	4.92		

Table 2 indicates significant gender differences in social media usage, self-concept clarity, and self-esteem. Females reported higher daily social media use (M = 5.28) than males (M = 4.32), while males scored higher on both self-concept clarity (M = 34.10) and self-esteem (M = 22.84). These results support Hypothesis 3, which suggested that females are more likely to engage in appearance-based online presentation and may therefore experience lower clarity of self-concept and self-worth compared to males. The findings reinforce the idea that gender moderates the psychological impact of social media on identity.

Table 3 : Correlation Matrix of Social Media Use, Self-Concept, and Self-Esteem (Pearson’s r)

Variable	1	2	3	4
1. Social Media Usage	—			
2. Self-Concept Clarity	-0.41**	—		
3. Self-Esteem	-0.36**	0.55**	—	
4. Social Comparison	0.48**	-0.44**	-0.39**	—

Note. * $p < .01$. Higher usage is linked with lower self-concept and esteem, and higher comparison tendencies.

Table 3 shows that higher social media usage was significantly correlated with lower self-concept clarity ($r = -.41$) and lower self-esteem ($r = -.36$), while being positively associated with social comparison ($r = .48$). In turn, social comparison was negatively related to both self-concept clarity ($r = -.44$) and self-esteem ($r = -.39$). These results strongly support Hypothesis 1, which proposed that greater social media use reduces self-concept clarity, and Hypothesis 2, which anticipated that reliance on comparison and validation processes would negatively impact self-esteem. The positive correlation between self-concept clarity and self-esteem further highlights the close link between stable identity and higher self-worth.

Table 4 : One-Way ANOVA: Cultural Differences in Online Identity Expression (N = 200)

Group (Culture)	n	M (Identity Expression Score)	SD	F	p
Western	70	28.75	5.10		
Asian	65	31.20	4.85	6.28	.002
Middle Eastern	65	30.45	5.25		

Qualitative Findings

1. Many participants described their online identity as “more polished” than their offline selves.
2. Female participants reported greater pressure to maintain physical attractiveness, while males emphasized achievements and humor.
3. Both groups acknowledged the temporary nature of validation-driven self-esteem, often leading to repeated cycles of posting and seeking approval.

Discussion

The present study sought to investigate the role of social media in shaping self-concept and identity among adolescents and young adults. A descriptive and inferential analysis was conducted on the relationship between social media use, self-concept clarity, self-esteem, and social comparison, with attention to gender and cultural variations. The findings are discussed below in the light of existing literature and theoretical frameworks.

1. Descriptive Insights

The descriptive statistics (Table 1) revealed that participants, on average, spent nearly five hours daily on social media, which is consistent with recent reports of high screen time among youth (Twenge & Campbell, 2018). The mean self-concept clarity and self-esteem scores indicated a moderate level of identity stability and self-worth, suggesting that while social media provides opportunities for self-expression, it may also contribute to fluctuations in identity perception. The relatively high score for social comparison aligns with Festinger’s (1954) social comparison theory, which posits that individuals constantly evaluate themselves against others, a tendency amplified by the curated nature of online platforms.

2. Gender Differences

The t-test results (Table 2) demonstrated significant gender differences across all three variables. Females reported higher daily usage of social media compared to males, echoing findings by Tiggemann and Slater (2017), who emphasized adolescent girls’ heightened engagement in

appearance-focused online interactions. Interestingly, males scored higher on both self-concept clarity and self-esteem, whereas females reported lower levels. This finding resonates with Perloff's (2014) claim that social media disproportionately exposes young women to idealized beauty standards, potentially lowering self-concept and self-worth. These differences highlight the gendered dimension of online identity construction and reinforce the importance of considering social media's psychological effects within cultural and gender-specific contexts.

3. Relationships Between Variables

The correlation analysis (Table 3) provided evidence of a strong negative relationship between social media usage and self-concept clarity as well as self-esteem. These results support Higgins' (1987) self-discrepancy theory, which suggests that discrepancies between the actual self and the idealized online self can lead to diminished psychological well-being. Moreover, a strong positive correlation emerged between social media usage and social comparison, implying that increased time online intensifies evaluative comparisons with peers. This pattern aligns with findings by Valkenburg and Peter (2011), who noted that online interactions magnify both opportunities for self-expression and risks of harmful comparison. The positive correlation between self-concept clarity and self-esteem further supports Rosenberg's (1965) view that self-worth is grounded in stable and coherent identity formation.

4. Cultural Variations in Identity Expression

The one-way ANOVA results (Table 4) revealed significant differences in online identity expression across cultural groups, with Asian participants reporting higher scores than their Western counterparts. This finding may be explained through Chen's (2013) perspective on cultural communication, which highlights the collectivist orientation of many Asian societies where social validation and group belonging are more central to identity formation. In contrast, Western participants, rooted in more individualistic cultural frameworks, may engage in online identity presentation with greater independence, leading to lower reliance on external validation. These cultural variations affirm McKenna and Bargh's (2000) argument that online spaces are not culturally neutral but instead reflect offline cultural values and expectations.

5. Theoretical Implications

The results of this study are consistent with Goffman's (1959) dramaturgical perspective, wherein social media functions as a stage for continuous self-presentation. Participants with high social comparison tendencies may strategically craft their online identities to align with socially desirable images, reinforcing short-term boosts in self-esteem but potentially undermining long-term self-concept clarity. The interplay of high social media use, comparison, and reduced clarity underscores the paradox of online self-expression: while these platforms facilitate exploration and connection (Davis, 2012), they may simultaneously intensify insecurities and identity confusion (Andreassen et al., 2017).

6. Practical Implications

Although not the primary focus, the findings offer practical insights. Educational institutions, parents, and mental health professionals may use this evidence to encourage balanced social media use and promote digital literacy programs that emphasize critical engagement rather than passive comparison. Understanding gendered and cultural nuances can further aid in designing targeted interventions to foster healthier identity construction in digital environments.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that social media has a profound influence on the formation of self-concept and identity. While it provides a stage for self-expression and social connection, it also fosters dependency on external validation and increases vulnerability to social comparison. The descriptive and inferential analyses confirm that higher social media usage is linked to reduced self-concept clarity, with notable gender differences in patterns of online identity expression. Overall, the findings reveal the dual-edged nature of social media: a tool for empowerment and creativity, but also a source of psychological strain in identity development.

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Sports' Role in Sculpting Indian Youth Identity and National Culture

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Abstract:

This paper explores the multifaceted and dynamic influence of competitive sports on the construction of youth identity and its contribution to the national culture of India. With over 1.4 billion people, India presents a unique sociopolitical landscape where unifying forces are paramount. Sport, particularly mass-appeal disciplines like cricket, field hockey, and kabaddi, serves as a powerful agent of social cohesion and collective self-concept. Utilizing a mixed-methods research design—encompassing comprehensive surveys of youth, in-depth interviews with key sporting figures, and observational analysis of sports events—this study investigates how athletic participation and spectatorship foster a cohesive national narrative. The findings unequivocally demonstrate that sports significantly impact the psychosocial identity of Indian youth, cultivating core values such as discipline, resilience, teamwork, and an intensified sense of national pride and unity that transcends regional, linguistic, and socio-economic divisions. The implications of this research are critical for policymakers, educators, and sports administrators aiming to strategically leverage the cultural and psychological power of sports for comprehensive youth development and the strengthening of national solidarity.

Introduction: Sports as a Cultural Unifier

In the colossal and diverse nation of India, the role of sports extends far beyond mere physical recreation or entertainment; it is a deeply ingrained cultural phenomenon that acts as a vital crucible for forging a collective national consciousness. Despite its vast mosaic of regional dialects, religious practices, and varied ethnic histories, India frequently finds its most potent expression of unity on the global athletic stage. This study delves into the psychological and sociological mechanisms through which this unity is transmitted, specifically focusing on its impact on youth identity formation.

The scholarly consensus, as highlighted by works in global sports sociology (e.g., Maguire, 2006; Giulia Notti, 2005), posits that competitive athletics are critical for defining both individual self-concept and collective national narratives. For the youth, engagement with sports—whether as athletes or passionate spectators—provides a “social identity” intricately linked to national heritage and aspirations. This process is particularly pronounced in India, where the victories and struggles of national teams are often internalized as a proxy for national progress and self-esteem.

The Pillars of Sporting Influence:

The profound influence of sports on young people can be distilled into three interconnected psychological and social mechanisms:

Cultivation of National Pride and Allegiance: Sporting events, especially international tournaments, transform into arenas for expressing collective national identity. When an Indian team triumphs, the emotional investment of the public translates into a potent surge of patriotism and allegiance. This collective effervescence momentarily dissolves internal boundaries, replacing them with a singular, unified “Indian” identity.

The Embodiment of Core Cultural Values: Disciplines like cricket, field hockey, and kabaddi are not just games; they are cultural texts that narrate an Indian ethos. The commitment of athletes like Sachin Tendulkar (for perseverance) or Milkha Singh (for struggle and triumph) serves as a moral compass, promoting idealized national values such as discipline, integrity, self-sacrifice, and relentless hard work.

A Shared History and Narrative: India’s sporting history—from the dominance of field hockey in the mid-20th century to the global ubiquity of modern cricket—provides a shared cultural memory. This history is continually reinforced by contemporary achievements, giving young people a tangible, emotional connection to their national past and future.

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Despite this evident importance, empirical research explicitly mapping the psychological pathways from sports engagement to youth identity and national culture in the specific Indian context remains underdeveloped. This paper aims to meticulously address this gap, moving beyond anecdotal evidence to provide a robust, data-driven analysis.

Conceptual Framework: Sports, Identity, and Soft Power

To fully grasp the scope of this study, it is essential to establish a clear conceptual framework that links individual psychology to mass social phenomena.

The Psychology of Identity Formation:

Identity, in psychological terms, is a structured sense of self, shaped by personal traits, goals, values, and social affiliations. For youth (ages 18–25), the stage of identity versus role confusion (Erikson, 1968) is paramount. Sports provide a safe and structured domain for experimentation with roles and the internalization of self-defining attributes. When a young person engages in a sport, they internalize the values associated with it (e.g., fairness, resilience) and adopt the social label of an “athlete” or a “fan,” thus building a robust personal identity.

Social Identity Theory and National Culture:

Social Identity Theory (SIT), championed by Tajfel and Turner (1979), is the crucial lens for understanding the collective aspect. SIT posits that a person’s self-concept is derived from perceived membership in relevant social groups (ingroups). For Indians, the nation is a primary ingroup. Sporting success enhances the perceived status of the national ingroup, leading to a phenomenon called “Basking in Reflected Glory” (BIRGing), where individuals feel better about themselves by association with a winning team. This psychological mechanism directly fuels the sentiment that “sports unite Indians across different cultures and regions.”

The Soft Power of Sport and Community Building:

Expanding on the sociological analysis of Giulianotti (2005), the paper adopts a model arguing that the development of Indian sports is an interdependent system driven by three main factors: International Partnerships, Community Building (Soft Power), and Domestic Sports Development.

Soft Power: Sport acts as a classic tool of soft power (Nye, 2004)—the ability to influence through attraction and co-option rather than coercion. The success of a national team or a popular domestic league attracts global attention and investment. This process of community building is vital; it challenges the prevailing stereotypes that often limit career aspirations to one or two major sports by demonstrating that success, recognition, and financial reward are achievable across multiple disciplines.

International Partnerships: The model emphasizes that foreign investment, experienced coaches, and technical staff are attracted only when a sport demonstrates a potential fanbase and organizational maturity. Partnerships with established international leagues or clubs inject world-class knowledge and expose Indian athletes to higher competition standards.

Interdependence: A strong, passionate, and well-educated sporting community (Soft Power) makes India an attractive investment destination, fueling International Partnerships. These partnerships, in turn, raise the quality of the sport, which further increases domestic passion and fan following.

Research Methodology: A Mixed-Methods Approach

This study utilized a robust mixed-methods research design to ensure both the generalizability of quantitative data and the rich contextual depth of qualitative insights. This comprehensive approach allowed for triangulation of data, ensuring the validity of the findings regarding the link between sports and identity.

Research Design and Data Collection:

Survey Research (Quantitative Data): A structured questionnaire was administered to 1,000 Indian youth aged 18–25 years. Participants were selected using a random sampling technique across various colleges and universities throughout India to ensure regional diversity. The survey measured attitudes toward sports, participation rates, and the perceived influence of sports on personal identity and national sentiment.

Demographics: The sample comprised 60% Male and 40% Female respondents, all of whom were college/university students. A high percentage of 70% reported participating in sports regularly, indicating a strong baseline interest in the subject matter.

In-Depth Interviews (Qualitative Data): Thirty semi-structured interviews were conducted with a diverse group of sports icons, coaches, and senior sports administrators. These purposively sampled participants were chosen for their deep, expert knowledge and experience in the Indian sports ecosystem. The interviews sought nuanced perspectives on athlete development, infrastructure challenges, and the psychological role of sports in fostering national character.

Participant Observations: On-site observations were conducted at major sports events and local competitions. Detailed field notes were taken to document the emotional climate, spectator behavior, levels of patriotism, and observed manifestations of teamwork and fair play among young athletes and fans.

Data Analysis

Quantitative Analysis: Survey data were analyzed using SPSS software. Descriptive statistics established baseline findings (e.g., participation rates), while inferential statistics explored the strength of correlation between variables like sports participation and reported national pride.

Qualitative Analysis: Interview transcripts and observation notes were processed through NVivo software. Thematic analysis and coding techniques were applied to identify recurring themes, such as the perceived impact of political influence, the need for better grassroots development, and the personal experience of feeling "Indian" through sports.

Core Participation Findings (Cross-Gender Analysis)

A crucial finding emerged from the participation data, which contrasts the competitive engagement rates between genders:

Category	Male Respondents (n=600)	Female Respondents (n=400)
Competitive Sports Participation (Yes)	88.1%	76.5%
No Competitive Sports Participation (No)	11.9%	23.5%

While both genders show high engagement, the 11.6 percentage point gap in competitive participation suggests a discrepancy in opportunity, resource accessibility, or cultural encouragement. The higher non-participation rate among female respondents (23.5% vs. 11.9%) warrants further policy attention regarding infrastructure, safety, and cultural barriers that limit young women's competitive sporting careers.

Results and Detailed Analysis

The findings of this study provide empirical support for the hypothesis that sports profoundly shape both youth identity and national culture in India.

Sports and Individual Youth Identity

The quantitative results underscore the personal, psychological impact of sports on the surveyed youth:

Identity Shaping: A significant 80% of respondents strongly agreed that sports play a fundamental role in shaping their identity. This suggests that sports provide a crucial framework for self-understanding beyond academic or familial roles.

Personality Development: 75% of youth affirmed that involvement in sports helps them develop vital personality traits. The most commonly cited traits were discipline, teamwork, leadership, and resilience—qualities that are highly valued in the Indian educational and professional spheres. The structured, high-pressure environment of competition is a key agent in this psycho-social molding.

Sports and National Cultural Unity

The unifying power of sports across the national landscape was strongly validated:

Surge of National Pride: An overwhelming 90% of respondents reported feeling intense pride in their Indian identity when national teams achieve success in international sporting events. This data is the strongest evidence of the BIR Ging effect, demonstrating that sporting victory is instantaneously and broadly translated into a collective sense of national worth and efficacy.

Social Cohesion: 85% of respondents believed that sports successfully unite Indians across various linguistic, cultural, and regional fault lines. This confirms that major sports acts as a cultural lingua franca—a shared emotional experience that temporarily overrides the heterogeneity of the population, fostering a singular, pan-Indian identity.

Qualitative Insights: Obstacles and Aspirations

Interviews with sports icons and administrators provided critical context, highlighting structural challenges:

Infrastructure Deficit: The qualitative data repeatedly stressed the need for enhanced sports infrastructure and consistent funding. This goes beyond just stadiums to include grassroots development, modern training facilities, and investment in sports science and technology (e.g., performance monitoring, injury recovery protocols, and data analytics), which are often lacking outside of elite cricket.

The Problem of Selective Privatization and Political Influence: A key obstacle identified was the selective privatization of sports, which disproportionately funnels resources, sponsors, and media attention toward one dominant sport (cricket), starving others. Furthermore, the issue of political influence in governing bodies—where, as noted, a substantial percentage of sports leadership lacks practical sports knowledge—was cited as a major drag on genuine, meritocratic sports development (Srivatsava & Atreya, 2020).

Discussion: Leveraging Sports for National Development

The research confirms that sports are an invaluable, yet under-leveraged, asset for national development. The collective fervor generated by sports provides a unique opportunity to in still values, strengthen social fabric, and elevate India's global standing.

The Policy Imperative for Multi-Sport Excellence

While the cultural impact of sports is clear, the current structure limits the nation's true sporting potential. The findings necessitate a policy shift away from a 'one-sport nation' mentality toward multi-sport excellence. This requires strategic intervention in two core areas:

Investment in Human Capital: The high participation rates, even with limited resources, signal a vast reservoir of untapped talent. Transparency in scouting and grassroots development is non-negotiable. Programs must be established that are free from financial or political bias, offering equal opportunities and robust sports education (including nutrition, injury management, and psychology) to young athletes from all socio-economic strata.

Structural and Technological Modernization: Achieving global competitiveness is impossible without closing the technological gap with European and North American sports organizations. This means mandating investments in sports science, data analytics, and providing technical staff trained in the latest methodologies. The push to host internationally acclaimed tournaments (e.g., the FIFA U-17 World Cup, as cited) is a proven catalyst for accelerating infrastructure upgrades and exposing the grassroots level to world-class standards.

Community Building through Shared Spectatorship

The study highlights that a well-developed and educated sporting community is an essential prerequisite for attracting investment and sustaining development. If non-cricket sports can generate houseful crowds with equal enthusiasm, the economic rationale for investment becomes self-evident. This requires innovative marketing strategies and improving the in-stadium experience to make watching all sports a high-quality, enjoyable, and accessible family activity, thereby strengthening the emotional and financial bond between the audience and the sport. The creation of strong, local, and regional fan communities for diverse sports reinforces the "soft power" concept, ultimately benefiting the country's image and influence globally.

Conclusion, Limitations, and Recommendations

The conclusion of this research strongly affirms that sports are a powerful, dual-edged tool, serving as a mirror and a forge for Indian youth identity and national culture. Participation and

spectatorship cultivate vital character traits, while success on the global stage acts as an unmatched source of national unity and collective pride, transcending the country's diverse geography.

Limitations

While comprehensive, this study had inherent limitations:

Sample Skew: The survey sample was limited to college/university students, which may introduce a bias towards a higher socio-economic or more educationally privileged demographic. Further research should include youth from non-academic backgrounds.

Qualitative Scope: While 30 interviews provided depth, a wider pool of athletes across a greater variety of sports would enrich the understanding of discipline-specific challenges.

Recommendations for Policy and Practice

To fully capitalize on the potential of sports to shape a dynamic youth identity and strengthen national culture, the following recommendations are offered:

Mandate International Partnerships: Federations and clubs should be strongly incentivized to enter long-term partnerships with established international entities to facilitate the exchange of coaching expertise, training resources, and administrative best practices, thereby accelerating the catch-up in competitive standards.

Ensure Non-Selective, Transparent Resource Allocation: Implement policies to prevent the selective channeling of private and public funds toward a single sport. Establish independent auditing bodies to ensure transparency in scouting and grassroots funding to eliminate political and financial bias.

Promote Multi-Sport Spectatorship: Launch national campaigns focused on building a passionate fan base for non-cricket sports. This includes improving the event organization, game-day hospitality, and digital engagement to increase live attendance and television viewership, thereby driving the crucial Soft Power necessary for attracting future investment.

Integrate Sports Education and Science: Make sports science, psychological training, and nutrition education mandatory components of all national and state-level sports development programs to ensure that athletes are developed holistically, maximizing their long-term health and performance.

By strategically addressing these structural deficiencies and embracing sports as a fundamental psychological and cultural pillar, India can unleash its vast youth potential, secure its position as a multi-sport global power, and continually reaffirm its identity as a unified and aspiring nation.

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Issue of Social Justice in Early Buddhist Sangh

Awadhesh Kumar Sah*

Abstract

The early Buddhist Sangh which appeared in the 5th -6th -century BCE was a revolutionary social and religious organization that undermined existing hierarchies and discriminatory social behaviors in the Indian society. Based on the ideals of compassion, non-violence and moral equality, the Sangh institutionalized social justice by supporting inclusivity in caste, gender and ensuring ethical behavior and community welfare. This paper will discuss social justice philosophical conceptions in Buddhism, institutional processes that strengthened the egalitarian principles of the Sangh and the impact of such practices in the whole society. It emphasizes the importance of monastic discipline, female ordination, education, and moral outreach in the formation of community which is socially equal. Although the study has noticed the weaknesses and the shortcomings of the Sangh, it also highlights its long-term goal of serving as a source of inspiration in the current quest of equality, human dignity, and social reform.

Key words : Buddhist Sangh, Bhikkhuni, Bhikhu, Sheel, Karuna, Samadhi, Nibban.

1. Introduction

The concept of social justice, which is equitable, equal, and dignified to all, has had a tradition of affecting the philosophical and ethical discourses in civilizations. However, the established socio-religious order in ancient India was characterised by a strict caste structure and gender imbalance. The birth introduced a stratified society of four varnas with the Brahmins, the Shudras and the so-called outcastes being pushed aside and marginalized in the social life. Even women were frequently deprived of agency, and reduced to domesticity, excluded even of intellectual or spiritual influence.

It is in this context that the emergence of Buddhism around the 5th -6th century BCE marked the beginning of a new social historic epoch in Indian history. The Buddha challenged the validity of privileges of birth, denying how moral value or religious capacity could be transmitted. Rather, he promoted a different definition of human dignity in which ethical behavior (sila), wisdom (panna), and mental discipline (samadhi) were the real determinants of social rank and position.

The key concept to the institutionalisation of this vision was the formation of the Sangh, the monastic community of monks (bhikkhus) and subsequently nuns (bhikkhunis). The Sangh was not just a religious fraternity, it was a radical experiment of creating an alternative social order that was grounded in inclusivity and equality. Its doors were open to everyone, irrespective of their castes and economic status, including those who were considered untouchable in the modern world, and thus Sangh formed a microcosm of justice that questioned the inequalities of the surrounding world.

The Sangh also managed an even wider sphere of influence outside its monasteries. The involvement of its members with the lay communities was through sermons, adjudication of disputes and promotion of charity and acts of social responsibility. Its alms-based economy undermined the caste and class boundaries, as the rich and the poor were equally involved in the support of the monastic order. The ordination of women into the Bhikkhuni Sangh, though with some hierarchical regulations, also disrupted the traditional gender patterns as both the rich and the poor were meant to support the monastic order.

However, the ideals of Sangh were not met very perfectly. The Brahmanical traditions resisted it, the pressures of patronage of kings and elites, and the internal strains against gender hierarchy are some of the difficulties that the egalitarian ethos of the Sangh had to confront.

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The analysis of social justice in the early Buddhist Sangh is consequential thus due to various reasons. To begin with, it emphasizes an Indian historical custom of equality and reform, which is much older than the rhetoric of rights. Second, it shows the importance of religious and philosophical institutions as the means of social change. Third, it offers timeless lessons to the modern fight against discrimination and injustice, especially in multicultural and stratified society.

This paper will discuss the problem of social justice within the early Buddhist Sangh in a systematic way. The subsequent parts examine the philosophical basis of equality in the Buddhist tradition, the institutional aspects of the Sangh, its interaction with the society at large, the ethical and moral aspects of justice and its wider legacy. Though the article recognizes its drawbacks, it asserts that it was the Sangh that introduced an effective and spiritual system of social justice that still guides the present-day equality, dignity and social reform movements.

2. Philosophical Foundations of Social Justice in Buddhism

The radical reconsideration of the human dignity, equality and the ethical responsibility is the philosophical basis of the social justice within Buddhism. The Buddha propounded an agenda at a time when caste hierarchy and gender based discrimination were rife in the Indian society, a time when hereditary privilege had long been the order of the day and moral worth was the hallmark of the individual. This stand is explicitly expressed in the *Vasala Sutta* wherein it is stated that a person is not born a Brahmin or an outcaste but becomes one by actions and thus this position became a major ground on which a social order of egalitarianism was founded. This philosophy was reflected in the Sangh as a living institution which in its turn accepted people of all castes and walks of life including untouchable ones and gave them an opportunity to pursue the highest spiritual aims.¹

Buddhism also based its vision of justice on the principle of karma, which was not viewed as a predetermined fate that individuals get because of the birth but as a moral law which is created by voluntary activities (*cetana*). In contrast to other interpretations that were mostly orthodox and justified social inequality as the harvest of previous lives, the Buddha focused on responsibilities in the present, which allowed individuals to transcend the situations and at the same time undermine the privileges of the elite who based their superiority on the descent. Through this, karma came to be a philosophical belief of justification, which balanced responsibility with the chance of change.²

Another main concept of the Buddhist concept of social justice is the concept of compassion (*karuna*), which also applies to every being. The *Metta Sutta* does not acknowledge the distinction between goodwill and its absence, therefore, the Sangh limits no limits in the spread of goodwill, regardless of differences in caste, gender or classes.³ Compassion was not just a personal virtue as a personality, but an institutional one since the Sangh lived on alms and regular contact with society, taking care of the ill, advising the troubled and guiding the moral way of the lay people.

Another moral basis of justice was the principle of non-violence (*ahimsa*). The *Dhammapada* states: "Everyone shudders with violence; everyone is afraid of death. One must put themselves in the shoes of somebody not to kill or make someone to kill. Violence of any kind, physical, verbal or structural was to be abandoned. In the Sangh, this rule prohibited exploitation, abuse of power or coercion and in the society, it promoted peaceful coexistence. Non-violence was thus not only an act of moral position, but a philosophical social doctrine of defending the dignity of every living being.

Another philosophical ground of justice is in the philosophy of dependent origination (*pratityasamutpada*), which rejects natural or permanent identity.⁴ As everything and every phenomenon is the result of conditions, no caste or category can boast of eternal superiority. This understanding breeds humility, equality and an appreciation of collective responsibility to the conditions that have created suffering. Because of this, social inequality is no longer perceived as something that cannot be changed, but rather through joint ethical effort. This is also represented in the Middle Path as advocated by the Buddha and in which there are neither extremes of indulgence nor deprivation, but a sense of balance. This was socially to create a just world in which neither a privileged nor deprivation should prevail.

The Buddhist Sangh in its nature institutionalized some sort of moral meritocracy. The superiority and respect were pegged not on wealth, power, or birth, but on seniority of ordination and observance of moral discipline.⁵ The most esteemed in the Sangh was the poorest village dweller or the lowliest worker so long as they adhered to the principles of virtue and wisdom. Through this, even early Buddhism, not only gave voice to, but was an enactment of a revolutionary philosophy of justice in its day, and was thus among the first organizations of social equality in Indian history.⁶

3. Institutional Practices and Social Justice

Early Buddhist Sangh with its institutional structure was in the middle of the process of transforming the abstract ideals of equality and compassion into the practical forms of social life. The Sangh was created as a community of the Vinaya (code of monastic living) that focused on living with discipline, ethical life and mutual respect among the families without any differentiation of birth and social status. The Sangh also chased after inclusivity by admitting people of all varnas, including the members of marginalized groups, especially the Śūdras and the outcastes, which set a precedent in Brahmanical order and uplifted caste distinctions. Decision-making in the monastic congregations was collective and premised on consensus, and reflected the democratic spirit of Sangh. This consultative institutional dependence on collective authority to a great extent reduced the hierarchical dominance and encouraged a feeling of equality in society.⁷

Moreover, women were the first among the religious bodies to institutionalize them with the Bhikkhunī Sangh, even though the systems then were patriarchal. Although there were other conditions where women could be ordained, the fact that, during monastic life, they were allowed to participate in it was an indicator that there was a progressive way of achieving gender justice by providing them with education, spiritual growth and social mobility. Social justice principles were also applied by the Sangh to both the internal organization and to the laymen, promoting acts of generosity (dana), proper livelihood and fair treatment of all creatures. Through this, the monastic practice did not only redefine spiritual life but also gave new models of ethical social order.⁸

The wealth reallocation by giving alms and the denunciation of personal property at the Sangh strengthened economic justice concepts, which opposed the material disparities of the modern world. The Sangh provided a different type of system (exploitation and accumulation) by encouraging communal property and voluntary simplicity. In addition, the teachings carried by itinerant monks and nuns of the Sangh critiqued violence, untouchability and entrenched caste-based discrimination thereby establishing social justice in the daily discourse. Even though not devoid of restrictions, including the stronger control over the role of women, institutional activities of the early Buddhist Sangh had a tremendous change to the strict social stratifications of ancient India and preconditioned the creation of a more rational and humane society.⁹

4. Social Outreach and Public Engagement

The Buddhist Sangh at its early form did not exist in an inside scope of the monks and nuns but it was able to interact with the rest of society in order to advocate justice, compassion and moral behaviour. As the Buddha stressed, the Sangh was to be in touch with the laity not only to enable it to make livelihood but also to help it discharge its moral duty of social transformation. Alms-rounds (pindapata) went beyond being a source of livelihood; it was also a sign of interdependence between Sangh and lay population, which served to support the principles of generosity, respect, and non-discrimination. When compared to caste-related limitations that denied some groups spiritual care, Buddhist nuns and monks were preaching to kings, merchants, peasants, and even outcastes and helped break down a strict stratum and establish a moral inclusivity sense.¹⁰

Sangh involvement into the public was also stretched to the promotion of moral values based on the Four Noble Truths and the Eightfold Path that dealt directly with human suffering and social factors that led to it. Teaching right livelihood (samma-ajiva), the Sangh provided an ethical comment on exploitative careers, including slavery, slaughtering animals, and unfair trade. These teachings led to the development of a moral economy, in which justice was associated with fairness, compassion, and sustainability. The monks usually played the role of mediating in the conflicts, and they offered

their advice according to the principles of non-violence (ahimsa) and reconciliation, and this made them more effective agents of social peace.¹¹

Another area of the Sangh outreach the Sangh set up monastic centers along trade routes and urban centers, where monasteries served as places of refuge, education, and moral discourse by local people. The monasteries turned out to be the centers of literacy, traditional medicine medical care and charity, which were an indication of the social service that the Sangh was devoted to. Unlike the exclusivist religious institutions, the monastic practices of Buddhism were designed to invite the laymen in the rituals, in learning and in making of merits thus democratizing the access to both spiritual and moral resources. By these outreaches and initiations, the Sangh did a lot in promoting social justice by cutting through the boundaries of caste, gender and class, besides establishing groundwork on ethical operations and social reforms in the Indian ancient world.¹²

5. Ethical and Moral Dimensions

The social justice vision of the early Buddhist Sangh could not be separated with ethical and moral grounds on which it was based. The Sangh had stressed upon the principles of sila (moral conduct), karuna (compassion), and metta (loving-kindness) as defining the conduct of life, and as contributing to the personal transformation as well as group harmony. These were not values that were confined to spiritual growth but had significant social connotations. To illustrate, the Five Precepts (panca-sila), which included not killing, not stealing, not engaging in sexual misconduct, not telling lies, and not taking intoxicants, was aimed both at the lay and monastic, hence establishing a common moral basis that crossed caste and gender boundaries. Through mutual responsibility and restraint which were encouraged by the Sangh, the society evolved to perceive justice not solely as a legal requirement but as a moral practice lived.¹³

One of the most important ethical contributions of the Buddhist religion was the doctrine of ahimsa (non-violence), which was not only applied to human relationships, but also to animals and nature. This ethical principle was the one which weakened hierarchical ideas about superiority and confirmed the ultimate value of being. The idea of dependent origination (pratityasamutpada) further supported the idea of moral responsibility by demonstrating that personal choices are bound to have some impact on the larger social and cosmic life. In these teachings, the Sangh promoted the principles of equality, compassion and accountability which were a direct challenge to the existing systems of inequality.

The Sangh moral code also placed a lot of relevance on the transformation of self as the beginning of social justice. The Eightfold Path and especially its elements of Right Speech, Right Action and Right Livelihood included a deliberate renouncement of exploitative activity and damaging occupations, thus entrenching morality in the economic and social association. By so doing, Buddhism did not define ethics as abstract ideal standing but as the dynamics of developing a just community. The development of such virtues as generosity (dana) and equanimity (upekkha) also guaranteed the fact that monastic and lay communities collaborated in the process of creating compassionate and egalitarian society.¹⁴

So, the ethical and moral aspects of the early Buddhist Sangh offered a unique pattern of justice which was based not on force and penalization but on self-restraint through willingness, compassion and acknowledgment of interdependence. This is one of the ethical visions of Buddhism that have continued to make a significant contribution to the social justice discourse.

6. Legacy and Contemporary Relevance

The quest of the early Buddhist Sangh towards social justice is much further reaching its historical setting and has continued to manifest itself in ethical, social, and political discourse in diverse cultures. The Sangh, rejecting caste systems, making spiritual practice open to women and giving spiritual emphasis to compassion toward all living beings provides a very early basis of egalitarian ideals that find echo in modern values of democracy, human rights, and social redress. Its demands on collective decision-making by assemblies anticipated participatory forms of governance

in the present and its denial of ritual exclusivity anticipated future views of institutionalized inequality. These donations show that the Sangh was a religious and social reform movement.¹⁵

In the modern world Buddhist ethics have been redefined and used to solve the urgent problems like gender justice, economic inequality, and environmental sustainability. Such trends as Ambedkar Navayana Buddhism in India emphasize the lasting applicability of Buddhist teaching to the anti-caste opposition and social liberation. On the same note, active Buddhism both in Asia and the West has been relying on Sangh ideals to deal with war, poverty and ecological crisis and has placed compassion and non-violence as a driving force in social change. The secular education, health, and welfare programs also are inspired by Sangh education, moral development, and community service in the world.¹⁶

But the legacy of the Sangh is not that simple. The limitations to women in monasticism and the difficulty in maintaining the egalitarian ways of life in hierarchical societies remind us of the limitations of the institutions of the early Buddhism. However, these restrictions do not reduce its timeless contribution but rather emphasize the necessity to redefine Buddhist values to fit the modern situation. The moral focus of the Sangh on metta (loving-kindness), karuna (compassion) and upekkha (equanimity) offers a model on how to establish inclusive societies based on dignity, respect and justice.

Therefore, the ancient Buddhist Sangh can be viewed as a historical model of a social change as well as an ongoing tradition that can be used to influence the discourse of equity, justice, and human prosperity in the contemporary world.

7. Conclusion

The early Buddhist Sangh was a radical socio-religious organization which aimed at reestablishing the human relations on the level of equality, compassion, and moral responsibility. Sangh was an alternative to the previous model of life in the society, which is highly fragmented along the caste lines, sex discrimination, and economic disparities. It codified the inclusion of women by including members of mixed social classes, institutionalized the inclusion of women, and focused on methods of alms, decision-making by consensus, and ethical livelihoods into tangible social justice policies.

Even though the Sangh was not devoid of restrictions, especially in its attitude towards women with extra regulations and its attempt to fully overcome the deep-rooted caste biases, it was still a revolutionary new step in the current trends of exclusion and subordination. Its ethical perspective focused on the fact that the right justice can be found not through force and coercion, but through self-renewal and a free will to live morally.

The lasting contribution of the Sangh is that it has succeeded in linking social reform with spirituality. Its teachings remain the source of inspiration of contemporary anti-caste, anti-gender, and anti-ecological balance movements, and the applicability of Buddhist morality is eternal. In this regard, the Sangh was not merely a religious organization but one of the earliest institutions of social justice the teachings of which are still very important in the creation of a more inclusive and caring world today.

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A Cross-Linguistic Study of Word-Order Patterns in Arabic, English, and French

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Abstract:

The paper discusses the position of direct and indirect objects, adverbs and adjectives of three languages: Arabic, English and French. It also states different word-order related to direct and indirect objects in Arabic.

Keywords: direct object, indirect object, adverb, *dharf*, *hæl*, adjective.

1. Introduction

Position of words vary from language to language. Studying comparative word order of the languages Arabic, English and French in relation to the position of objects, Adverb and adjective placement will be discussed in this paper. This will help the learners of Arabic as a foreign language to understand its word order in relation to English and French.

2. Position of direct and indirect object in Arabic, English and French languages:

2.1. Position of direct and indirect object in Arabic:

In Arabic language we don't have direct and indirect object, we have first object and second object according to its position whoever comes first is a first object and the second is a second object. Intransitive verbs in Arabic are those verbs which are not taking any object, while transitive verbs are those verbs which are taking one object or more.

For example:

A'ata Abdullah Mohammadan kitaban.

V S first object second object

Gave Abdullah Mohammad a book

Abdullah gave Mohammad a book.

As we have seen, according to Arabic grammar *Mohammadan* is a first object and *kitaban* is a second object. But if we put *kitaban* before *mohammad* in the sentence then *kitaban* only will be object.

For example:

A'ata Abdullah kitaban leMohammad.

V S O Preposition Noun

Gave Abdullah book to Mohammad

Abdullah gave a book to Mohammad.

In the above example, *A'ata* is a past tense verb means 'gave'. *Abdullah* is a subject noun. *Kitaban* is an object means 'book'. The prefix *le-* is a preposition letter means 'to'. *Mohammad* is a noun of preposition tool. In Arabic any noun comes after preposition tool will be a noun of that tool.

Note: In Arabic language there are seven verbs taken three objects. Those verbs are (*a'ra*, *a'alama*, *a'nba'a*, *nabba'a*, *akhbara*, *khabbara* and *haddatha*) mean (explain, told, told, told, told, told and told).

For example:

A'alama aljundeyu alqae'da ala'duwa qadiman.

V S First object Second object Third object

Told the soldier the commander the enemy coming

The soldier told the commander that the enemy is coming.

2.2. Position of direct and indirect object in English:

The answer of the interrogative pronoun what in English will be the direct object wherever the position of object, while the answer of the interrogative pronoun for who / for whom will be an indirect object. English has two types of verbs, first one is intransitive verbs mean those verbs which are taking only one object, and the second is transitive verbs mean those verbs which are taking two objects.

For example:

Mohammad ate an apple.

In the above sentence, we have only one object and it is a direct object because it is the answer of what Mohammad has eaten? He ate an apple.

Mohammad gave Abdullah a pen.

In the above sentence, the answer of what Mohammad has given? Will be a direct object (a pen). The answer of for whom Mohammad gave a pen? Will be an indirect object (Abdullah). Mohammad gave a pen to Abdullah.

In the above sentence the direct object is a pen and the indirect object is Abdullah.

2.3. Position of direct and indirect object in French:

2.3.1. Position of direct and indirect object:

In French the verb is linked with the direct object. Usually direct object preceded the indirect object

For example:

Sandeep donne un stylo à Magid.

S V article direct object indirect object

Sandeep gives a pen to Majid.

Here, the direct object preceded the indirect object.

2.3.2. Position of direct object pronoun and indirect object pronoun

If a direct and an indirect object pronoun are used in the same sentence we usually put the indirect object pronoun before the direct object pronoun. But if the direct and indirect object pronoun are belong to third person singular or plural the order will be reversed and we put the direct object pronoun before the indirect object pronoun.

For example

Ahmad vous l'envoie demain.

S Indirect object pronoun Preposition Direct object Adverb

Ahmad sends it to you tomorrow.

In the above sentence, *Ahmad* is a subject noun. *Vous* is an indirect object pronoun means 'it'. *L'* is a preposition tool means 'to'. *envoie* is a direct object pronoun means 'you'. *Demain* is an adverb means 'tomorrow'.

Je les lui ai lus.

S direct object pronoun indirect object pronoun aux V

I read them to him.

Ne la leur donne pas.

Negative tool direct object pronoun indirect object pronoun V Negative tool (ne.....pas)

Don't give it to them.

To distinguish between direct and indirect objects in French language, the general rule is that if the preposition à or pour followed the person or thing, that person or thing is an indirect object. If that person or thing is not preceded by a preposition, it will be direct object. If the noun or thing preceded by any other preposition, it can't be replaced by an object pronoun.

3. Position of Adverbs in Arabic, English and French languages:

3.1. position of adverbs in Arabic sentences:

Adverbs in Arabic language is called *Alhæl* which is unknown noun describes the situation or the manner. To describe place and time in Arabic we used unknown noun called *dhurf* which is divided into two types *Dhurf Alzaman* and *Dharf Almakan* which mean ‘adverbs of time and adverbs of place). As we have mentioned Arabic has three types of adverbs as follow:

- *Dhurf Alzaman* Adverbs of time
- *Dhurf Alzaman* Adverbs of place
- *Alhæl* Adverbs of manner

3.1.1. Dhurf Alzaman:

Dhurf alzaman means ‘Adverb of time’ is a noun used to indicate the time of action. Always the answer of interrogative pronoun *mata* means ‘when’ will be an adverb of time. There are many nouns used to indicate an adverb of time in Arabic, but we will mention some of it with examples in following table to show the word-order of time adverbs.

Word-order of time adverbs in Arabic language					
Adverb of time	Meaning	Example			
		Verb	Subject	Object	adverb
<i>Albariha</i>	Last night	Kataba	Mohammad	Aldarsa	Albariha
		Wrote Mohammad the lesson last night Mohammad wrote the lesson last night. Last night Mohammad wrote the lesson.			
<i>Ghadan</i>	Tomorrow	Sayaktubu	Mohammad	Aldarsa	Ghadan
		Will write Mohammad the lesson tomorrow Mohammad will write the lesson tomorrow. Tomorrow Mohammad will write the lesson.			

Adverbs of time occur at the beginning or at end of the sentence in Arabic language.

3.1.2. Dhurf almakan:

Dhurf almakan means ‘Adverbs of place’, is a noun used to indicate the place of action. Always the answer of interrogative pronoun *a'yna* means ‘where’ will be an adverb of place. There are many nouns indicated adverbs of place in Arabic, but we will mention some of it with examples in following table to show the word-order of place adverbs.

Word-order of place adverbs in Arabic language					
Adverb of place	Meaning	Example			
		Verb	Subject	Adverb of place	Adverb of time
<i>huna</i>	Here	<i>Jalasa</i>	<i>Mohammad</i>	<i>huna</i>	<i>Albariha</i>
		Sat Mohammad here last night Mohammad sat here last night. Last night Mohammad sat here. Here Mohammad sat last night. Here last night Mohammad sat.			
<i>Khalifa</i>	Behind	<i>Jalasa</i>	<i>Mohammad</i>	<i>khalifa</i>	<i>albayt (noun)</i>
		Sat Mohammad behind the house Mohammad sat behind the house. Behind the house sat Mohammad. Albariha behind the house sat Mohammad. Albariha sat Mohammad behind the house.			

In Arabic, Adverbs has no fix place it can move from anywhere to anywhere in a sentence.

3.1.3. Alhæl:

Alhæl means 'adverb of manner' is an unknown noun describes the manner of the verb occur at the beginning or at end of a sentence.

For example:

Saqa Mohammadun alsayarata mosria'an

Verb Subject Object Adverb

Mohammad drove the car quickly.

Albariha Saqa Mohammadun alsayarata fee alqaryah. mosria'an.

Adverb of time Verb Subject Object adverb of place manner of adverb

Last night drove Mohammad the car in the village quickly

Last night Mohammad drove the car in the village quickly.

mosria'an Saqa Mohammadun alsayarata fee alqaryah albariha.

Quickly drove Mohammad the car in the village last night.

Note: Arabic Adverb has no fix position in the sentence, usually it occur at the end of the sentences, but if we want to put emphasis on it then the position of adverb will be changed. For example:

Kataba Mohammad aldarsa alu'sbuo' almadi fee albayt bea'jalatin.

V S O time adverb place adverb manner adverb

Wrote Mohammad the lesson last week at house quickly

- If we ask by interrogative pronoun when the answer will be:
Last week Mohammad wrote the lesson at house quickly.
- If we ask by interrogative pronoun where the answer will be:
At house Mohammad wrote the lesson last week quickly.
- If we ask by interrogative pronoun how the answer will be:
Quickly Mohammad wrote the lesson last week at house.

3.2. Position of adverbs in English sentences:

The position of English adverbs is like the position of Arabic adverbs, they have no fix position, it can occur at the beginning, mid and at the end of a sentences. In the following table we will mention some adverbs of English to show how it move according to emphasis.

Position of adverbs in English sentences.		
Type	Position	Example
Manner	-Usually occur at the end of a sentence - But sometimes occur in mid of a sentence	He drives the car quickly. He quickly drives the car.
Time	-Usually occur at the end of the sentence - But sometimes occur in front of a sentence if we want to emphasis the adverb	I will go tomorrow. Tomorrow I will go.
Place	-Usually occur at the end of the sentence - But sometimes occur in front of a sentence if we want to emphasis the adverb	They have taken their dinner here. Here, they have taken their dinner.
Frequency	-Usually occur in mid of a sentence -sometimes occur at the beginning of a sentence - sometimes occur at the end of a sentence	My son usually helps me. Sometimes my son helps me. He doesn't visit me very often.

As we have seen in the above table, English adverb moves in the sentence according to emphasis.

3.3. Position of adverbs in French sentences:

Adverb is one part of speech that modifies a verb, adjective or another adverb. There are six rules for adverb placement in French language, the following rules apply to majority of situations of adverbs, and there are exceptions.

- If an adverb modifies a verb, the adverb placed after the conjugated verb.
- If an adverb modifies an adjective or another adverb, the adverb placed in front of that word.
- Adverbs of place are usually placed after the direct object.
- Adverbs of frequency are usually placed after the verb.

- Adverbs of time that refer to specific time can be placed at the beginning or at the end of the sentence.
- In negative sentences adverbs that would normally follow the verb are placed after the second part of the negation tool (pas). For example:

Je ne mange pas bien.

S Negation V Negation Adverb

I don't eat well.

Some of the most common Adverbs with examples			
Adverb	Type of adverb	Meaning	Example
<i>Actuellement</i>	Adverb of time	currently	<i>Actuellement je travaille en Inde.</i> Adverb S V Preposition N Currently Im working in India.
<i>Aujourd'hui</i>	Adverb of time	Today	<i>Aujourd'hui ils iront à l'école.</i> Adverb S V Preposition N Today they will go to school.
<i>Bientôt</i>	Adverb of time	Soon	<i>Bientôt mon père rentrera.</i> Adverb Adjective possessive N V Soon my father will come back.
<i>déjà</i>	Adverb of time	Already	<i>J'ai déjà mangé.</i> S Aux Adverb V I have already eaten.
<i>demain</i>	Adverb of time	Tomorrow	<i>Demain je partirai en France.</i> Adverb S V Preposition N Tomorrow I will go to France.
<i>enfin</i>	Adverb of time	Finally	<i>Enfin j'ai réussi.</i> Adverb S Aux V Finally I have succeeded.
<i>ensuite</i>	Adverb of time	Next / then	<i>Ensuite je vais regarder le match.</i> Adverb S Aux V Article N Then Im going to watch the match.
<i>hier</i>	Adverb of time	Yesterday	<i>Hier il faisait froid.</i> Adverb S V Adjective Yesterday it was cold.
<i>longtemps</i>	Adverb of time	For long time	<i>Longtemps je ne t'ai pas vu.</i> Adverb S Negation (nepas) direct object pronoun V For long time I didn't see you.
<i>maintenant</i>	Adverb of time	Now	<i>maintenant j' étudierai.</i> Adverb S V Now I will study.
<i>Tard</i>	Adverb of time	Late	<i>Viens tard!</i> V Adverb Come late!
<i>tôt</i>	Adverb of time	Early	<i>Viens tôt!</i> V Adverb Come early!
<i>ici</i>	Adverb of place	Here	<i>Viens ici!</i> V Adverb Come here!
<i>là</i>	Adverb of place	There	<i>Vas là!</i> V Adverb Go there!
<i>là-bas</i>	Adverb of place	Over there	<i>Regarde là-bas!</i> V Adverb

			<i>Look over there!</i>
<i>partout</i>	Adverb of place	Everywhere	Je trouve <i>partout de l'eau</i> . S V Adverb Preposition N I find water everywhere.
<i>quelque part</i>	Adverb of place	Somewhere	<i>quelque part j'ai oublié mes clés</i> . Adverb SAux V Adjective possessive N Somewhere I lost my keys.
<i>bien</i>	Adverb of manner	well	Il parle <i>bien</i> . S V Adverb <i>He speaks well</i> .
<i>heureusement</i>	Adverb of manner	Fortunately	<i>malheureusement j'ai oublié mes clés</i> . Negation Adverb S Aux V Adjective possessive N Unfortunately I lost my keys.
<i>mal</i>	Adverb of manner	Poorly	Il s'habille <i>mal</i> . S V Adverb <i>He dress up poorly</i> .
<i>vite</i>	Adverb of manner	Quickly	Il travaille <i>vite</i> . S V Adverb He works quickly.
<i>Assez</i>	Adverb of quantity	Quite / fairly	J'ai <i>assez mangé</i> . S Aux Adverb V I have quite eaten.
<i>beaucoup</i>	Adverb of quantity	A lot	Je t'aime <i>beaucoup</i> . S Direct object pronoun V Adverb I love you a lot.
<i>peu</i>	Adverb of quantity	Few / little	Donne-moi <i>peu!</i> V Pronoun Adverb <i>Give me little!</i>
<i>très</i>	Adverb of quantity	Very	Il est <i>très beau</i> . S V Adverb Adjective He is very handsome.
<i>trop</i>	Adverb of quantity	Too much	Il mange <i>trop</i> . S V Adverb He eats too much.
<i>aussi</i>	Comparative adverb	as	Ils sont <i>aussi beaux</i> . S V Adverb Adjective They are as handsome.
<i>Moins</i>	Comparative adverb	less	Elle est <i>moins jolie</i> . S V Adverb Adjective She is less beautiful.
<i>plus</i>	Comparative adverb	More,....-er	Il est <i>plus gentil</i> . S V Adverb Adjective He is more kind.
<i>parfois</i>	Adverb of frequency	Sometimes	<i>Parfois Sandeep mange beaucoup</i> . Adverb S V Adverb. <i>Sometimes Sandeep eats a lot</i> .
<i>souvent</i>	Adverb of frequency	Often	Je vais <i>souvent au cinéma</i> . S V Adverb Preposition N I often go to the cinema.
<i>toujours</i>	Adverb of frequency	Always	<i>toujours</i> Il mange <i>beaucoup</i> . Adverb S V Asverb <i>Always he eats a lot</i> .

4. Position of Adjective in Arabic, English and French languages:

4.1. Position of Arabic adjectives: Adjective is a word describes the noun. In Arabic usually noun precedes an adjective but sometimes Adjective precedes noun. Adjectives in Arabic agree with the nouns in number and gender. Some words can function as adjective in a sentence such as: derivative noun, preference noun, demonstrative noun, relative noun and number. For example:

- Derivative name → *Haḍa katibun mahir.*
 Demonstrative noun N Adjective
 This writer skilled
 This writer is skilled.
 This is a skilled writer.
- Preference pronoun → *Shahadtu rajulan a'shjau' mena ala'sad*
 V S O Adjective Preposition N
 Saw I a man more courageous than lion.
 I saw a man more courageous than lion.
- Demonstrative pronoun → *sa'adtu Mohammadan haḍa.*
 V S O Adjective
 helped I Mohammad this
 I helped this Mohammad.

Here, *haḍa* is a demonstrative noun means 'this' function as adjective. If there are many people named Mohammad and one particular is chosen then the sentence will be used.

- Relative pronoun → *faza altalibu allaḍi darasa bejed.*
 V S Adjective V Preposition N
 Won student who studied hard
 The student who studied hard won.

In the above sentence, the whole clause *allaḍi darasa bejed* which mean 'who studied hard' all together represents an adjective.

- Number → *fee alssufi tulabun arba'una.*
 Preposition N N number
 In the class Students forty
 there are forty students in the class.

Here, the number *arba'una* means 'forty' function as adjective.

Note: always noun precedes the adjective in Arabic. Adjective called in Arabic *Tawabi'e* means 'followers', here we mean by followers those adjectives which follow the nouns and agree with it in number, gender and in the motivation marker called *Harakat altashkee* which we will explain it in the third chapter verb-agreement. But there is only one type of adjective in Arabic called *nae't sababi* where the adjective precedes the noun. For example:

Haḍihi shajaratun laḍeeḍatun thimaruha.
 Demonstrative pronoun N Adjective N
 This is tree delicious fruits its
 The fruits of this tree is delicious.

Haḍa hissanun a'byadun lawnohu.
 Demonstrative pronoun N Adjective N
 This is a horse white color its.
 The color of this horse is white.
 This is a white color horse.

4.2. Position of English adjectives:

Adjectives of English not agree with the noun which it is modified in number and gender unlike Arabic and French adjectives. Adjectives in English language could be before the nouns or after the nouns in a sentence.

For example:

This is a small table.

This table is small.

This is a black table.

This table is black.

These are a good boys.

These boys are good.

Those are a good girls.

Those girls are good.

As we have seen in all of the above examples always the form of adjectives is same, it will not change even if the noun is singular or plural number and masculine or feminine gender.

4.3. Position of French adjective:

Usually adjective in French language follows the noun unlike English, but there are some adjectives in French precede the nouns such as:

The Word order of adjective in French language is:

Subject + V+O+ Adj

J'ai une table ronde.

S V Article N Adjective

I HAVE a round table.

Here, *j'* is a subject which means 'I'. *ai* is a verb which means 'have'. *Une* is an indefinite article which means 'a'. Table is an object. *ronde* is an adjective which means 'round'.

Nous avons une robe verte.

Np V article N adjective

We have a green dress.

But there are some exceptional adjectives which preceded the nouns such as:

Exceptional adjectives which are preceded the noun					
Adjective	Meaning	Adjective	Meaning	Adjective	Meaning
Beau	Handsome	Jeune	Young	Petit	Small
Bon	Good	Joli	Pretty	Premier	First
Court	Short	Long	Long	Vieux	Old
Grand	Big	Mauvais	Bad	Une belle journée	A lovely day
Gros	Large	Meilleur	Better	Bonne chance!	Good luck
Haut	High	Nouveau	New		

Also there are some adjectives placed before or after the noun according to context.

Exceptional adjectives which are placed before or after the noun				
Adverb	Meaning	Example/ before noun	Meaning	Example/ after noun
Ancien	Former	<i>un ancien collègue.</i> A former colleague .	Old	<i>un fauteuil ancien.</i> An old chair.
Cher	Dear	un t-shirt cher Dear friend	Expensive	<i>un t-shirt cher.</i> An expensive t-shirt
Propre	Own	<i>ma propre chambre.</i> My own bed room.	Clean	<i>un mouchoir propre.</i> A clean handkerchief.

Conclusion

- Adverbs in all three languages have no fixed position in the sentence. It could be at the beginning, middle or at the end of the sentence depending on the focus of the sentence.
- An adverb of manner is only called an actual adverb in Arabic language. Adverb of time is called *dhurf zaman* and adverb of place is called *dhurf makan*.
- In Arabic language any object occurs first in the sentence will be the first object, the second one will be the second object and the third one will be third object. If the object occurs after

preposition it will not be object it will be *E'sim majror* (any noun follows the preposition will be the noun of that preposition).

- There are seven verbs in Arabic which take three objects.
- In English usually direct object precedes the indirect object. The answer of the interrogative pronoun *what* in English will be the direct object wherever the position of object, while the answer of the interrogative pronoun *for who / for whom* will be an indirect object.
- French language has direct and indirect object also has direct and indirect object pronoun. Usually direct object of French language precedes the indirect object. While the indirect object pronoun precedes the direct object pronoun, but if the direct and indirect object pronouns belong to third person singular or plural the order will be reversed.
- Adjectives of Arabic language always follow the nouns. There is only one exceptional case in which the adjective precedes the noun when the type of adjective is *nae't sababi*. Arabic adjectives must agree in gender and number with the noun it modifies. Arabic adjectives, therefore, have six forms: masculine singular, feminine singular, masculine dual, feminine dual, masculine plural and feminine plural.
- Adjectives of English can precede or follow the noun.
- In French language usually adjectives follow the nouns, but there are some exceptional adjectives which precede the nouns. Also there are some Adjectives could precede or follow the nouns. French Adjectives must agree in gender and number with the noun it modify. French adjectives, therefore, have four forms: masculine singular, feminine singular, masculine plural, and feminine plural.

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